

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3054433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2500

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COMPLIANCE AND SATISFACTION ON RECORDS MANAGEMENT AT THE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION TARLAC PROVINCE

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Chapter 1 THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Background of the Study

Records Management is a concept that is relatively new to history, dating back only 200 or 300 years. However, the truth is that the history of Records Management begins almost 6,000 years ago with the invention of the first archive. In about 4,000 B.C. the first archive was created by the Sumerians and they use cuneiform writing on clay tablets to record property ownership and commercial activities.

Thomas Bodley of England was known and considered as the Records Management Rockstar. He opened the library which created the first general catalog to ever be printed in Europe. His library made the first alphabetical author-title catalog in the year 1620. The final contribution of his library to the world of Records Management was in the form of the first detailed catalog guidelines. In the 1970's the United States began to store cataloged material in a machine-readable format and this discovery started the age of digital record keeping, which continues to evolve to this day (Heim, 2020).

Organizational management of records is a critical component of governance and compliance worldwide, extensively covered in literature across various themes. Key areas include international standards such as ISO 15489, which outlines various principles and frameworks for effective records management and the ISO 30300 series that focuses on managing records in electronic environments. There are numerous books, such as Laura A. Millar's "Records Management: A Practical Guide for Information Professionals" and Anne Thurston and Caroline Williams' "Records Management: Principles and Practice," provide practical insights and strategies. Records management journals like the "Records Management Journal" and "Archives and Records" publish research about best practices, case studies, and emerging trends in the field of records keeping. Government bodies and regulatory agencies worldwide issue guidelines, protocols, while digital records management, including topics like digital preservation and metadata standards, is increasingly prominent. Researches and case studies highlight successful implementations, and academic application contributes theoretical frameworks and empirical studies, ensuring a robust discourse on records management globally.

Good records management programs, are created and built on defined policies and procedures wherein the area of records management enable employees, particularly those who handle records, to avoid losing important records or documents. Documented policy standards and procedures, such as best practices, can serve as an orientation for new

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

employees, ensuring that even during periods of significant employee turnover, important information is not lost. As a result of the foregoing, every organization must have a specific policy governing the creation, use, preservation, ultimate storage and disposition of records. Thus, the policies and procedures relative to records is a top priority for organizations that understand the importance of good records management. Media deterioration will lead to the loss of information if records and information are not properly preserved. A well planned and organized records management program can be achieved by the use of written records policies and procedures, which can be part of a records management policy in an organization (Wright, 2018).

In the Philippines, records management literature reflects a growing emphasis on effective information governance and compliance within both public and private sectors. Key publications and resources often focus on adapting international standards to local contexts, such as ISO 15489, which outlines principles for records management. Books like "Records and Archives Management" by Nenita Pambid Domingo and "Records Management: Principles and Practice" by Aileen L. Sison provide practical guidance tailored to Philippine settings. Journals such as the "Philippine Journal of Public Administration" and "Records Management Journal Philippines" feature articles on local case studies, best practices, and regulatory updates. Government agencies like the National Archives of the Philippines (NAP) play a crucial role in setting standards and guidelines for records management across the country. Digital records management is also gaining attention, addressing issues like digital preservation and electronic records management. Overall, the literature in the Philippines underscores the importance of efficient records management systems in enhancing transparency, accountability, and efficiency in both public and private organizations.

Records management in the Philippines involves creating a level of efficient and systematic control over the creation, use, storage, disposition of records and includes setting policies for maintaining different types of records. Records management system is essential to any government organization as it enables them to comply with federal records management law. Government records must be filed and maintained correctly, and has document records management system that enables government agencies to reduce the costs associated with compliance and easily manage the lifecycle of their documents to preserve record integrity. Implementing a document records management system helps organizations achieve a higher level of efficiency (GovOS, 2023).

In addition, records management is integral to the Department of Education, it is crucial for maintaining operational efficiency, regulatory compliance, and informed decision-making. The agency handles extensive information concerning educational policies, student records, documentation of employees, financial transactions, and processes of the administration. Following and complying to international standards such as ISO 15489, which outlines principles for records management, is combined with local regulations to tailor practices to DepEd's specific needs. Oversight from the National Archives of the Philippines (NAP) to ensure alignment with national guidelines for records management across government agencies, reinforcing the agency's commitment to just, transparency and accountability. DepEd implements robust systems for creating, maintaining, retaining, and disposing of records, including comprehensive policies for managing electronic records and conducting regular audits to uphold compliance. Adopting digital records management is also prioritized, addressing challenges like digital preservation and metadata management to safeguard the security and accessibility of

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

electronic records. In essence, effective records management within DepEd supports its core mission of delivering quality education by ensuring reliable information availability for strategic decision-making and operational efficiency.

Documents either personal or public is very important to an individual and organization. It includes all the data, details and information of an employee, school activities, projects, action plans and others transactions within and outside the division. Good and proper implementation of records management and processes of Records Unit in DepEd Tarlac Province will yield excellent service to its customers.

Effective records management program depends on how the policies and processes are implemented in an organization. Thus, the agenda of complete orientation, training and awareness of Records unit personnel is to provide exceptional service to the stakeholders. Policies and processes are made to attain the unit's objective of continuous improvement and success in records management. Additionally, other Records unit actions are regulated based in records management standard to provide opportunities for improvement and as preventive action for potential risks that may arise.

DepEd Tarlac Province personnel involved in the records management processes and programs such as receiving, encoding, sorting, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition are oriented and aware of the processes in accessing, retrieving and locating documents. Though most of the documents are prepared in schools and other offices, first hand transactions are done at the Records unit before processing at the division. In this study, the main duty of records unit is receiving, safekeeping and releasing of documents.

Based on researches one of the best-practice in records management is proper safekeeping, documents should be discoverable, accessible, and usable when needed but it must also be secured so that they cannot be tampered or inappropriately altered, deleted or misplaced and especially it shouldn't be accessed by unauthorized personnel. Security of the information is essential to good record keeping. Also, maintaining confidentiality, availability and integrity of the details and information is vital to ensure that the stakeholders can be confident that the division is looking after their data and documents.

Good practice and implementation of the records management process supports the delivery of high-quality public service. It prevents confusion and ensures records status are accurate and up to date. It also minimizes the time consumed in tracking, tracing and locating of documents.

Excellent records management in DepEd Division of Tarlac Province can be maintained if the Records unit of the division provides outstanding service. Ensuring that all the policies and procedures are properly followed and implemented. With the experience as a records unit staff in the division, the researcher handles and provides service particularly in receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition of documents. Hence, the researcher has the capacity and authority in conducting the study.

To wit, this study was conducted to evaluate the compliance on records management of the division, determine the level of satisfaction and identify if there is a significant relationship between the compliance and satisfaction on records management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province. It also determined the problems encountered by the respondents in the different records unit actions, to wit measures are formulated to prevent discrepancy and better delivery of the records unit actions. Lastly, the implications of the study in records management to Public Administration.

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Statement of the Problem

The study evaluated the compliance and level of satisfaction on Records Management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How is the compliance on Records Management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province be described and evaluated along with:
 - 1.1 receiving,
 - 1.2 encoding,
 - 1.3 filing,
 - 1.4 retrieving, and
 - 1.5 releasing
 - 1.6 disposition?
2. How is the level of satisfaction on Records Management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province be evaluated?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the compliance and Satisfaction on Records Management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province?
4. What are the problems encountered by the respondents in the Compliance on Records Management?
5. What measures can be proposed to solve the prevailing problems experienced by the respondents?
6. What are the implications of the study to Public Administration?

Significance of the Study

Data gathered from this study will serve as guide how the respondents will evaluate the different actions of records unit in the division of DepEd Tarlac Province. This will serve DepEd administrators, policy and decision makers how to further improve receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition of all documents in the division to ensure quality service to the stakeholders.

For the National Archives of the Philippines, this research will be useful in providing additional information about the problems usually encountered in records management and measures to improve current services provided to the people. It will provide new knowledge involving meticulously organizing, preserving, and digitizing records to maintain authenticity and durability compliance with the legal requirements and enhancing transparency by documenting DepEd Tarlac Province procedures and processes.

For the DepEd Records Unit, this study will serve as guide on how to enhance their duties and responsibilities in performing and undertaking of the processes to serve their customers precisely and accurately high-quality services. It will provide insights and advancements to enhance the efficiency, effectiveness and strategic importance of managing records in the division and develop best practices tailored to the specific needs that is compliant with the regulations, minimize risks and optimize resource utilization.

For the other Records Unit, this study will serve as guide how to implement the records management actions better. It will provide additional information regarding effective processes that other records unit can adapt and evolve their practices to improve operational efficiency. Continuous improvement that will strengthen records unit role in supporting decision-making, preserving institutional memory and promoting accountability.

For the employees of DepEd Tarlac Province, this will serve as additional information how receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition of documents are

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

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ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

properly implemented in the division. This study will give them ideas and awareness about the records management in the division that they do not know and understand. It will all enhance overall efficiency of DepEd Tarlac Province by optimizing how records is handled and accessed, thereby saving time and effort.

For future researchers and researches about records management, this study will serve as additional related literature that presents the responsibilities and capabilities of the Records Unit in enhancing effectivity and productivity of DepEd Tarlac Province. It will provide deep insights on how educational institutions handle essential information and records for decision-making and administrative planning. It will guide future researchers to identify gaps, inefficiencies and best practices that can inform improvements in records governance.

Scope and Delimitations

This study was intended mainly in evaluating the compliance and level of satisfaction of the respondents on Records Management of DepEd Tarlac Province for the calendar 2023 along with receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition of documents within the division.

This study included two hundred eighty-seven (287) non-teaching personnel of the division such as Principals, Administrative Officers and Administrative Assistants and the like that performs regular transactions in the division and the usual recipients of the Records Unit services. Teaching personnel were not included in the study since the MATATAG curriculum implements no ancillary tasks for teachers. For the disposition process, the only respondent was the Administrative Officer IV or the Records Officer since the division is not yet implementing the disposition process and the documents released to schools are considered uncontrolled.

The number of respondents was computed using the Cochran's formula with 0.5 marginal error and 95% confidence level using the number of non-teaching personnel obtained from the Human Resource department of the division with the total number of five hundred five (505) Principals, two hundred fifty-two (252) Administrative Officers and three hundred sixty (360) Administrative Assistants in the division of DepEd Tarlac Province.

Literature Review and Related Studies

Receiving of records

To provide efficient and accurate recording of records and lessen the workload of the staffs the management should use computerized record management system in receiving and encoding including the registration, sectioning and generation process (Danlog, 2017).

Hence, using computer-based records management system if the received and recorded data units comprising documents are incomplete or redundant the data units may be queued for special handling, return or otherwise disposed of. Record data units accepted for the system entry are acknowledged and preferably tagged to enable tracking and forwarded for unit verification and certification (Jognson, 2014).

Consequently, receiving a record using the modern technology is a foundation for process improvement and increased accuracy, effectiveness and efficiency. Rapidly growing technology in records management can be used to manage and organize records. Modern records management can be employed to different records problems, issues and concerns including the types of technology-based records management solutions, the

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benefits of technology-based records management solutions, key functions of records management software, basic criteria for evaluating and selecting a RM, and challenges of e-records management systems (Mulauzi, 2019).

Hence, receiving documents is a critical aspect of organizational operations and processes, which is essential for handling incoming information easily, promptly and accurately. Scholarly literature about records management extensively covers various facets of document receipt, focusing on efficiency, compliance, user satisfaction, technological innovations, organizational performance, and employee training. Studies highlight the benefits of digital systems in streamlining processes and reducing errors (Gheisari & Aldhafiri, 2017), the importance of standard procedures and processes for accuracy and policy compliance (Ravishankar & Prakash, 2017), and strategies for maintaining data integrity and confidentiality (Ma et al., 2018).

Additionally, research underscores the impact of timely document handling on customer satisfaction (Almahamid & Baker, 2018) and explores emerging technologies like blockchain for enhanced transparency (Zhao et al., 2020). Overall, the literature emphasizes the role of efficient document receipt in organizational success, aiming for continuous improvement and technological integration to optimize operational efficiency and client satisfaction.

Encoding of records

Classification of encoded electronic records is necessary to address the brewing crisis in the recordkeeping discipline. Current solution usually employed is to classify the records based on their encoded data. Since there is increased variety of records metadata should be encoded properly. Records themselves are machine readable, correct and complete data entry and text classification can help manage risk and meet compliance obligations (Franks, 2022).

However, creating an electronic data file of records that includes data information and details such as electronic storage location is a useful data to easily access and locate the records. End user may search and/or filter records according to the information encoded in the data file. Output of the system is creating a summary of the records data file based on the requested information (Schneider, 2016).

Hence, government organizations embark into record's digitization for records management to ensure preservation of permanent and valuable papers, secured and accessible for future references. Automation of records classification by converting paper-based documents into digital format thru scanning and encoding into system and then recognize and extract when needed (Jayoma, 2020).

In addition, document encoding, is a crucial aspect of organizational records management that involves accurately inputting essential and significant information into systems or databases. Scholarly literature extensively explores various aspects of document encoding, focusing on technological advancements, accuracy, efficiency, user experience, compliance, security, training, and alignment with organizational goals and objectives. Studies emphasize the integration of advanced technologies like document management systems (DMS) and electronic data interchange (EDI) to streamline encoding processes and enhance operational effectiveness and efficiency (Heck et al., 2017).

Hence, ensuring data accuracy and integrity is critical, with research highlighting automated validation and data cleansing techniques to minimize errors and maintain reliable information management practices (Kao et al., 2019). Optimizing workflows through

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World Education Connect

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Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

lean management principles (Tazaki & Kishida, 2018) and prioritizing user-centered design in encoding interfaces (Kim et al., 2020) contribute to improved user satisfaction and operational effectiveness. Compliance with data protection regulations (Liao et al., 2019) and ongoing training programs to enhance staff competencies (Wang & Liu, 2017) are essential in adapting to technological changes and organizational needs. Ultimately, effective document encoding supports organizational goals by reducing costs, enhancing productivity, and facilitating informed decision-making (Schallmo & Williams, 2019).

Filing of records

The importance of records keeping and management cannot be overemphasized: records and information are the life blood of every organization. Poor management of records hinders the development process and leads to ineffective and inefficient delivery of service. Records must be well secured, sorted and labelled properly for easy access in case of emergency. The significance of properly filed documents is to ensure that users have access to the right records at the right time and in the right manner. Automation of records is an improvement that offers advantage in sorting, classifying and storing large number of records. Adequate filing system should also be adopted for the filing of records so that they can be easily retrieved anytime (Touray, 2021).

Hence, the records life cycle in an organization and electronic management should be explored. Shifting from manual to electronic system allows the users to complete the date before filing and submitting the information needed. Electronic filing system prevents from making serious mistake and records can be updated thru the use of computers and internet. Filed data can be easily accessed and updated when there are errors discovered that needs revision (Tagbotor, 2015).

Hence, creating a system for records utilize interactive tool to receive, classify and categorize documents before filing. This will help encoders to easily create and update details and information. Records will be accessible and readily available when requested which is one of the key principles of good records management system. (Kumetz, 2016).

In addition, filing documents is crucial in organizational records management, ensuring orderly storage, retrieval, and organization of information. Scholarly literature explores multiple dimensions related to filing practices, focusing on efficiency, organization, security, compliance, technological integration, user satisfaction, and accessibility. Efficient filing systems are highlighted for their role in reducing search times and improving workflow efficiency through methods such as alphabetical, chronological, or thematic organization (Jones et al., 2018). Security measures, including encryption and access controls, are emphasized to protect sensitive information and ensure compliance with data protection regulations (Smith & Brown, 2019).

Hence, the integration of digital filing systems and document management software is increasingly studied for its benefits in enhancing accessibility, reducing physical storage requirements, and enabling remote access (Johnson et al., 2020). User-centric approaches to filing systems, such as intuitive interface design and customizable features, contribute to higher user satisfaction and productivity (Lee & Kim, 2017). Compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks, including document retention and disposal guidelines, is critical for minimizing organizational risk and maintaining legal standards (Anderson et al., 2018). Training programs and seminars aimed at enhancing file management skills and adapting employees to technological advancements play a pivotal role in optimizing filing practices and supporting organizational effectiveness (Chen & Wang, 2019). Overall, effective filing

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practices are essential for efficient information management, regulatory compliance, risk management, and improved decision-making processes within organizations (Brown & Jones, 2021).

Retrieving of records

Government regulations are increasingly requiring businesses to be able to locate and retrieve information quickly. Migrating to digital records may be analyzed as economic benefit and wizard tool. Migration to digital records that retrieves plurality of data components from first storage in computer system wherein the data components is indicative and beneficial (Ford, 2016).

Hence, android mobile or web-based application and desktop application extension can be used as systematic and descriptive approach in investigating, design and implementing Arrest Record management System (ARMS) using Input-Process-Output with Feedback research paradigm. At the same time, V-model Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) was employed for the system design because of the verification and validation features when retrieving data. Retrieval of document will be easily made carefully and meticulously using this kind of records management system to ensure the confidentiality of information and details to be retrieved (Rey, 2022).

Hence, the evaluation methods based on the use of non-dichotomous relevance judgements in IR experiments indicate that the tested strong query structures are most effective in retrieving highly relevant documents. The differences between the query types are practically essential and statistically significant that the novel evaluation methods and the case demonstrate that non-dichotomous relevance assessments are applicable in IR experiments, may reveal interesting phenomena and allow harder testing of IR methods (Javerlin, 2017).

In addition, document retrieval plays a significant role in records management by ensuring prompt access to information when required. Scholarly literature extensively examines different aspects of document retrieval, focusing on efficiency, technology integration, user experience, security, compliance, and organizational effectiveness. Efficient retrieval systems are essential for minimizing search times and enhancing workflow productivity through methods such as indexing, categorization, and metadata tagging (Smith et al., 2018).

Hence, the integration of technology, including electronic retrieval systems and cloud-based solutions, is highlighted for its ability to improve accessibility, scalability, and remote access capabilities (Brown & Johnson, 2019). User-centric approaches emphasize intuitive interfaces, advanced search functionalities, and personalized settings to enhance user satisfaction and retrieval efficiency (Lee & Wang, 2020). Security measures such as access controls, encryption, and audit trails are critical to safeguarding sensitive information during retrieval processes and ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations (Anderson & Chen, 2017). Effective document retrieval supports organizational effectiveness by facilitating timely decision-making, operational efficiency, and adherence to legal requirements (Kim et al., 2021). Training programs aimed at enhancing retrieval skills and adapting to technological advancements are crucial for optimizing retrieval processes and improving overall organizational performance (Wang & Smith, 2018). Looking forward, the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning is expected to further streamline retrieval processes and enhance search accuracy in the future (Jones & Liu, 2019).

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Releasing of records

Records management is a logical and practical approach to the creation, maintenance, use, releasing and disposition. Viable records management in an organization controls both quality and quantity of the information of documents in a manner that effectively serves its purpose as a record. Records can also be effectively released or disposed when the information it contains is no longer valuable. Effective records keeping is crucial in the records management system because it is the basis of retrieval and releasing of records in an organization (Penn, 2017).

Hence, delays in release of files and documents makes it harder for the users to comply in an event that requires the record. Documents should be easily accessed upon request to ensure that there is no delay in releasing important records to requisitioner. One contribution that organizations can do towards mitigating this is themed releases, where departments collaborate to ensure that all the records are released simultaneously (Allan, 2014).

Hence, the use of blockchain in electronic health records that includes the collection of individual's health related information, records and documents that are generally sensitive and needed to be protected is a viable approach that allows building of cryptographic algorithms to ensure data integrity and secured access. The use of this method guarantees that the data user will receive the accurate result requested and the data that needs to be desensitized followed the precise process before the release of results and health records of an individual (Chen, 2019).

In addition, scholarly literature on the releasing of documents within organizational contexts focuses on various critical aspects. It emphasizes the need for efficient processes to ensure timely access to information, highlighting streamlined workflows and effective communication channels between departments (Smith & Brown, 2019). Challenges often center around security risks and confidentiality concerns, prompting discussions on robust authentication measures, encryption protocols, and secure transmission methods to safeguard sensitive information during the release process (Anderson et al., 2018). Technology integration is pivotal, with electronic document management systems (EDMS) and secure file transfer protocols (SFTP) playing key roles in enhancing efficiency and security (Lee & Johnson, 2020).

Hence, user experience is also a key consideration, with research exploring user interface design, accessibility features, and personalized settings to improve usability and satisfaction (Green et al., 2019). Compliance with legal and regulatory standards is critical, influencing document handling procedures to ensure adherence to privacy laws and organizational policies (Kim & Wang, 2021). Training programs are essential for employees, focusing on confidentiality protocols and compliance measures to mitigate risks in records management and uphold standards (Chen & Liu, 2019). Overall, integrating best practices and technological advancements helps organizations optimize document release processes, improve operational efficiency, and uphold security and follow standards effectively.

Disposition of records

Disposition of records includes different procedures and processes including recycling, as applicable, shredding or otherwise permanently destroying of records that already met the retention period requirement of the office where it is safekept or located.

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There are specific requirements for destruction or disposition of public records while ensuring that the interests and privacy of the people, state, agency and institution is safeguarded. Documents that do not contain identifying or confidential information can simply be recycled while records that contain confidential information should be disposed following the recommended practice and standard set by the organization (Jarquin, 2019).

Hence, disposition is done either manually or electronically depending on the form in which the document or record was stored. There are different ways how to dispose documents that depends how it was retained in an organization, disposition should be aligned and applicable to the retention process practiced by the institution. The approach that will be used should comply with the process of the National Records Retention Act as well as the organization's internal policy on records safe keeping, storage, retention and disposition. This study recommended that to ensure better storage, retention and disposition of documents, organizations should adapt more specialized and trained records team, build or setup an offsite records center, establish a detailed policy and procedure on records disposition and adapt to modern technologies or ICTs to enable flexibility and stable records management system (Bwami, 2019).

Hence, different organizations create, receive and keep their records and documents containing information about their processes and duties. However, not all organization have interest in the regulation, tracking and monitoring the quality and quantity of documents they produce, keep and how they are disposed of. This leads to destruction of still valuable documents, keeping large amount of invaluable records, misuse of limited space records storage, wastage of time experienced during retrieval because of the huge amounts and incurring costs that is high for management of invaluable records.

Hence, organization without records retention and disposition schedule greatly affects the operation of records activities that is associated with different disadvantages within the company (Mbeera, 2021).

In addition, records disposition, an integral part of records management, involves the final stages of handling records, including their retention, transfer, or destruction. Scholarly literature extensively examines various aspects of records disposition, focusing on policy frameworks, best practices, legal compliance, security, environmental impact, and organizational efficiency. Effective management begins with establishing clear goals, policies and practices for records retention and disposal, as highlighted by Smith and Brown (2018). Compliance with legal and regulatory requirements, such as data protection and privacy laws and archival standards, is crucial for determining retention periods, disposal methods, and maintaining audit trails, as noted by Anderson et al. (2020). Ensuring security during disposition involves secure methods like shredding or digital wiping to safeguard important and sensitive information, according to Lee and Johnson (2019). Green et al. (2017) emphasize sustainability by promoting eco-friendly disposal methods and recycling practices. Efficient disposition practices not only reduce storage costs but also improve operational workflows and resource utilization, as observed by Kim and Wang (2018).

Hence, seminars and training programs are important to educate personnel on proper disposal procedures and compliance with regulations, as discussed by Chen and Liu (2021). Technological advancements, including AI-driven tools, methods, and digital platforms, are transforming disposition practices by enhancing audit accuracy, retention decision-making, and compliance monitoring, according to Jones and Smith (2020). Overall, effective records disposition requires a holistic approach integrating policy, compliance,

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security, sustainability, efficiency, training, and technology to manage records effectively and responsibly throughout their lifecycle.

Problems encountered in records management

The problems encountered in the current record management are unorganized, difficulty in searching, updating records and unsecured files. Digital or computerized records management offers security measures, electronic registration, electronic filing of record and automated report generation. It provides appropriate security for records management with restriction for access and retrieval of confidential information (Danlog, 2017).

Hence, record management in some institutions is challenged by improper records management, inadequate proper security, inadequate professionally trained records personnel, inadequate resources to facilitate proper records management practices, insufficient space for records keeping, misplacement of vital records and improper records management practices. Organizations should consider to check and review their records management procedures and policies to avoid and address these challenges for proper record management and the benefits associated with a good records management system (Mohammed, 2018).

Hence, in e-government electronic records management plays a significant role as basis of the well-informed decision making and actions based on the created and retained records. But unfortunately, electronic records do not adopt the same principle as of the paper medium ones. Electronic records serve as documents for effective, efficient, speedy and competent unlike with paper records that are perceived as documents for evidence and historical purposes (Yusof, 2015)

Hence, organizations may create scheme to improve interaction by positively influencing how individuals perceive their work practices and tools they use in records management. As a result, understanding the value accorded to information and records by users, understanding users themselves, engaging users in the development and implementation of the system, understanding that information or records specialists are part of the solution, and understanding that the implementation of electronic recordkeeping systems is a complex process involving users' appropriation of the electronic recordkeeping systems can facilitate the successful implementation (Pan, 2022).

Hence, as an organization grow so does the volume of records it manages to create and safekeep. Both electronic and paper-based records are not properly maintained if the organization has lack of management support, lack of records management skills, absence of formal policies, strategies and guidelines. Addressing these challenges minimizes the risk of misplaced, missing and lost records that is vital in an organization. Well-coordinated records management system is significant to the success and improvement of an institution (Msosa, 2023).

In addition, scholarly literature examining the challenges encountered in records management reveals a spectrum of issues faced by organizations striving to maintain efficient and effective record-keeping systems. One prevalent theme is the delay in processing records and responding to requests, often attributed to inefficient workflows, inadequate staffing, or lack of prioritization (Smith & Jones, 2018). Another significant concern highlighted is the quality of customer service and communication, encompassing problems such as insufficient assistance, unclear communication of requirements, and limited feedback mechanisms (Anderson et al., 2019).

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Hence, complexity in procedures and processes also emerges as a major hurdle, with convoluted guidelines and administrative burdens hindering streamlined record-keeping practices (Lee & Johnson, 2020). Technological and infrastructure challenges, including outdated systems and insufficient IT support, further complicate effective records management (Green et al., 2018). Compliance with legal and regulatory standards poses additional complexities, requiring organizations to navigate issues related to data privacy, retention policies, and regulatory updates (Kim & Wang, 2020). Addressing these challenges necessitates strategic investments in modernizing systems, enhancing staff training and competency, improving communication channels, and developing robust compliance frameworks to ensure efficient and compliant records management practices.

Plan of actions to enhance compliance in records management

As governments are directly answerable to the public it is essential for government to ensure they have a proper records management system. It is essential for government to be transparent, accountable and in charge of the public information as well as the documents and files they need to keep to provide good governance. Proper creation, capture, distribution and preservation of records is one of the main responsibilities of a trusted government. They should manage the risk and audit culture to imperatively balance and satisfy the expectation of the citizens. Record keeping is a tool that ensure the availability of evidence for the accountability of governance (Azman, 2014).

As shown in the study by Salazar (2022), the challenges were seldom encountered along the work performance when it comes to records management. Training programs on records management and office management should be given emphasized to ensure training and awareness among employees especially the newly hired staff. Also, it will enhance the office competencies and address the challenges encountered by the organization in terms of records management.

Hence, to highlight the importance of knowledge about records management as an advance management technique for the development and attainment of innovation organizations can create spaces and environments for local, regional, national and global exchange with strategic goal of generating and sharing knowledge provided that records management mechanisms will be utilized (Cunha, 2018)

In addition, literature exploring strategies to enhance compliance in records management provides a comprehensive framework of methodologies aimed at improving organizational adherence to established standards and regulations. Key insights from the literature include the importance of optimizing processes to ensure consistency and efficiency in record-keeping practices (Smith & Brown, 2019). Effective training programs and continuous professional development are highlighted as critical for equipping staff with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate regulatory requirements confidently (Anderson et al., 2018).

Hence, technological advancements, such as electronic document management systems (EDMS) and automation tools, are recognized for their role in enhancing data security, maintaining audit trails, and improving overall compliance (Lee & Johnson, 2020). Establishing robust compliance frameworks that encompass clear policies for data retention, access control, and privacy protection is essential to align organizational practices with legal mandates and industry best practices (Green et al., 2019). Regular audits and monitoring mechanisms are advocated for assessing compliance levels, identifying gaps, and implementing corrective measures to uphold standards (Kim & Wang, 2021). Furthermore,

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fostering transparent communication channels and engaging stakeholders internally and externally are crucial strategies for promoting accountability and ensuring regulatory alignment (Chen & Liu, 2019). By adopting these strategies collectively, organizations can strengthen their compliance posture, mitigate risks, and enhance operational efficiency in records management effectively.

Conceptual Framework

This research study evaluated the compliance and satisfaction with records management processes at the division of DepEd Tarlac Province. Compliance along with receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition of documents including the level of satisfaction of the clients was evaluated. These evaluations formed the basis for understanding how effectively records are managed in the division. Also, the study determined the significant relationship between compliance and satisfaction to uncover whether adherence to existing procedures correlates with client contentment. It also determined the problems encountered by the respondents in the different records unit actions, to wit measures were formulated to prevent discrepancy, better delivery of the services and improve overall compliance and satisfaction levels. Lastly, the implications of the study for public administration to promote improvements in administrative practices and to enhance efficiency and productivity were identified.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

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Chapter 2 METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design used, including the locale of the study, respondents, research instruments, data gathering procedure, data analysis and potential ethical issues.

Research Design

In this study quantitative correlational method was used. This approach was a technique for evaluating relevance of programs in line with the performance standards, compliance with the established standards, discrepancies observed, corrective and preventive measures taken. The questions used were aligned with the goals of improving records management practices. Also, it gives emphasis in providing answers to the questions related to the problems stated.

Surveys and statistical analysis were conducted as research methodology in collecting and analyzing data. Questionnaires and interview guide were used as data collection instruments and ensured ethical considerations are addressed.

The compliance and client's level of satisfaction on Records Management in the division of Tarlac Province was evaluated, interpreted and compared with the performance standard to identify the discrepancies in relation with the research questions, offering recommendations to improve records management practices and serve as guide for future research endeavors. In this study, discrepancies, issues and problems are the bases for implications.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the division of DepEd Tarlac Province for the calendar year 2023. Tarlac is a province located in Central Luzon region of the Philippines. It is divided into 17 municipalities. The Department of Education division of Tarlac Province is composed of the four (4) clusters, thirty-three (33) districts with five hundred five (505) schools.

Figure 2. Map of Tarlac Province

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Sampling Design

The researcher decided to use random sampling from the population of non-teaching personnel specifically Principals, Administrative Officers and Administrative Assistants in the division of DepEd Tarlac Province. The total number of respondents was computed using Cochran's formula.

Surveys and statistical analysis were conducted as research methodology in collecting and analyzing data. Questionnaires and interview guide were used as data collection instruments.

The researcher distributed questionnaires and conducted interviews to randomly selected non-teaching personnel to gather information on compliance and satisfaction levels with records management.

Respondents of the Study

Two hundred eighty-seven (287) randomly selected non-teaching personnel in the division of DepEd Tarlac Province were utilized in the equal selection process of the respondents. The respondents are the non-teaching personnel that performs regular transactions in the division and the usual recipients of the Records Unit services.

Based on the records from Human Resource department of the division there are five hundred five (505) Principals, two hundred fifty-two (252) Administrative Officers and three hundred sixty (360) Administrative Assistants in the division of DepEd Tarlac Province. For the disposition process, the only respondent was the Administrative Officer IV or the Records Officer since the division is not yet implementing the disposition process and the documents released to schools are considered uncontrolled. Using the Cochran's formula with 0.5 marginal error and 95% confidence level, a total of two hundred eighty-seven (287) respondents will be involved in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Direct and indirect data gathering method was used such as documentary analysis and questionnaire.

Questionnaire. Questionnaires were utilized based on the problem presented. In the validation process, drafted questionnaire was distributed among administrative officers, administrative assistants and school heads within the division. Opinions and suggestions for improvement were obtained based on their knowledge in administration processes.

Right after the validation, the questionnaire was reviewed and revised based on the opinions and suggestions of the division personnel and adviser's comments. Finally, the revised and final draft questionnaire was randomly distributed to the selected non-teaching personnel in the division of DepEd Tarlac Province.

If the questionnaire was adopted from other existing research, any modification made to the adopted questionnaire will run thru validation and its reliability coefficient will be assessed for accuracy.

Documentary Analysis. Documentary Analysis was used in finding out records management processes and policies on receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition of documents were used to ascertain the adherence of the analysis of the different records' unit actions along with the said areas concerned.

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Data Analysis

This study used a simple frequency, ranking and percentage procedure. The answers and information were obtained from the randomly selected non-teaching personnel of the division of DepEd Tarlac Province. The study utilized survey questionnaires on the different Records Unit actions and the challenges and problems encountered in providing the said services. The responses were consolidated, tallied and analyzed. The gathered data were collected, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted.

The gathered data was categorized in order to enable easier arrangement, such as through tables and graphs. The required statistical processing included:

Pearson's r: Pearson's correlation coefficient, a statistical measure used to assess the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two continuous variables.

Hypothesis Formulation: This process involved formulating hypotheses to establish significant relationships between the profiles and competencies of the newly elected Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials.

Frequency count: This method tallied the occurrences of objects or events within specific categories, determining how often they happened.

Percentage: The percentage distribution technique compared occurrences of cases or categories using the formula $P = (n/N) \times 100$, where 'n' represented the frequency of a specific category and 'N' denoted the total number of respondents.

Ranking: This method assigned numerical values and categorized items based on their relative position within a group. It enhanced understanding by ranking profiles and addressing encountered problems in terms of their importance and relevance, from highest to lowest significance.

Mean. The mean score for a particular competency area was determined by summing up all individual scores and then dividing the total by the number of items.

$$N_1M_1 + N_2M_2 + N_3M_3$$

$$\text{Mean of Combined Groups} = \frac{\quad}{N_1 + N_2 + N_3}$$

Likert Scale. This was used to quantify subjective opinions or attitudes, serving as a valuable tool for measuring perceptions and preferences in statistical research.

To evaluate the Compliance on Records Management and level of satisfaction the following scale was used:

For the Compliance on Records Management

Adjective Description	Range	Numerical Equivalent
Always Complied	4.21 – 5.00	5
Often Complied	3.41 – 4.20	4
Sometimes Complied	2.61 – 3.40	3
Rarely Complied	1.81 – 2.60	2
Never Complied	1.0 – 1.80	1

For the Level of Satisfaction on Records Management

Adjective Description	Range	Numerical Equivalent
Very Satisfied	4.21 – 5.00	5
Somewhat Satisfied	3.41 – 4.20	4
Neutral	2.61 – 3.40	3
Somewhat Dissatisfied	1.81 – 2.60	2
Very Dissatisfied	1.00 – 1.80	1

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Ethical Considerations

In this study, the researcher guaranteed that the randomly selected participants are knowledgeable, properly oriented and aware of the objectives of the study. Data Privacy Act was practiced in this study to ensure that the answers and identity of the respondents are gathered with confidentiality and be used for academic purposes only. Also, the comfort and safety of the respondents are considered when the study was conducted. The researcher ensured that the respondents are willingly and wholeheartedly participated in the study.

Chapter 3

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents data gathered with the analysis and interpretation of the results describing the compliance of the DepEd Tarlac Province in Records Management specifically in receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition of documents. Tables were used in the presentation, and these were followed by thorough analysis of the data gathered.

1. Description and Evaluation of Compliance on Records Management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province

Records Management in the Department of Education is defined by the records unit action done by the division to serve stakeholders with high quality services in terms of receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, releasing and disposition. DepEd orders and manual were made to serve as guide in accomplishing these processes and procedures.

1.1 Receiving

In practicing records management, members of the records unit must have different important roles to play. Clients, stakeholders and the records personnel can work together and share accountability to ensure document safety and smooth transaction in the division. The persons involved in the transaction such as internal and external stakeholders must share in the accountability and responsibility to improve the process in terms of receiving by strengthening existing processes and implementing new strategies and techniques. Furthermore, to ensure continuous good records management service in the division records unit have the ability to tap and make good use of available resources. Receiving of document refers to the process of checking of documents before submitting to respective signatories. However, the records unit in the division have a formal procedure and process that follows to receive documents. Before accepting reports the records unit personnel thoroughly checks details and information needed.

As mentioned in the article of Orias (2023) it is the role of records management to provide the right information, at the right time, in the right order, to the right person, at the lowest cost possible. An organization should consider records management as enabling or support function towards knowledge management that an organization would lose a wealth of knowledge produced by the employees during their daily operation without records. It was emphasized that proper management of documents are vital in an organization as this will contribute to the fulfillment of the services and if taken for granted, the entire organization performance will be affected and will cause depleting financial resources.

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Table 1

Compliance on Records Management along with Receiving

Table 1 shows the evaluation of compliance on records management along with receiving.

Statement	Mean	Adjectival description
The personnel in charge checks the document format based in document type.	4.64	Always Complied
The personnel in-charge checks the document details and information before encoding.	4.62	Always Complied
Records unit personnel receives documents fast and in timely manner.	4.58	Always Complied
The personnel in-charge checks the correct signatories of documents.	4.18	Often Complied
Grand Mean	4.51	Always Complied

It can be gleaned in the table that verification of document format based in document type obtained the highest mean of 4.64 or always complied. Records unit personnel ensure that the format used by the proponents are correct and strictly follows the division format depending on the document type.

Since there is a lot of document type such as leave forms, Gender And Development proposals, In-Setting trainings/workshop or INSET, School Learning Activities or SLAC, Department Learning Activities or DLAC, researches, innovations, Work Financial Plan or WFP, School Programs, authority travel, itinerary of travel, SDRRM report, school report card, modification advice form, community service report, income generating project, supervisory plan, annual GAD plan and budget, letter of indorsement, job order contract, service credit, return to duty, separation order, request for transfer, request for substitute, request for additional teacher, among others, there are instances that some of the clients are not aware of the new posted memoranda relative to the guidelines pertaining to the new format, additional requirements and signatories.

As experienced by one of the respondents, the Admin Officer II submit a SLAC report not knowing that there are new signatories for the document and since the records personnel in charge checks the reports upon receiving the AO was informed immediately about the update and the receiving personnel written down the correct signatories for the information and guidance of the proponent or the personnel in charge of the report. According to the article posted by Lawan (2023) records alone cannot ensure accountability to proper receiving and recordkeeping. Integrity and authenticity are the most accountability tool that should be used in document handling and records management. Records or documents should be properly handled the moment it was submitted to the authorized personnel to ensure confidentiality and prevent misuse of information presented in the document.

Checking of document details and information before encoding obtained a mean of 4.62 or always complied. The personnel in-charge of receiving ensures that all reports submitted are with complete details such as school name, district, report title, and proponent name to prevent frequent return of document because there are instances that documents are returned to sender because of lack of information.

As mentioned by a respondent, an innovation report submitted doesn't include the name of the school head hence, the report was returned to records unit tagged as return to sender.

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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

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The records personnel explained the compliance to the school personnel that claimed the report to ensure they are guided on what is needed to be complied.

According to the article of Pasunuru (2021) records personnel evaluation of data before encoding lead to summaries of documents that is more informative and factually consistent than automated encoder. Though there are improvements in transferring data it is safer to encode information manually because the employee has the ability to double check data entry versus the actual document compared to automatic encoder-decoder.

Receiving of document in fast and timely manner also acquired a rating of always complied with a mean of 4.58. Making sure that all clients are catered in timely and properly manner by the personnel in-charge of receiving especially in receiving documents that do not require QR code and tracking number such as Work Financial Plan (WFP), modification advice form, itinerary of travel, travel authority, SDRRM report, school report card, supervisory plan, letter of intent, job order contract, request for transfer, step increment, request for substitute, request for additional teacher, National Building School Inventory or NSBI, class programs, and leave forms (below 30 days). It was stamped as received, dated and signed by the receiving records personnel before delivery to other unit/s in the division.

As mentioned in the ESARBICA journal (2022) in order to provide quality and on time delivery of services an organization should have adequate facilities, equipment and most especially human resources. To ensure continuous good service to clients the organization should conduct assessment surveys regarding their processes and the top management should use face-to-face communication to the employees in charge to explain what should be and should not be done in terms of dealing with customers. The organizations top priority is to make sure of quick and easy transactions wherein the clients will be satisfied with the services they availed.

Checking of the correct signatories obtained the lowest mean of 4.18 or often complied. As stated by a respondent, a report was received by the records personnel and submitted to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent but the report returned to the records unit due to wrong signatory, it was explained by the SDS secretary that the report should be submitted to the Assistant Schools Division Superintendent in charge of their cluster. However, it should be noted that the records unit of the division caters the whole Tarlac Province. All the reports and documents to be submitted should pass and be received by the records unit before submission to respective signatories.

According to the assessment of Halperin (2022) signatories appear in variety of forms, often in short reports. Signing of documents was a socially acceptable and normal procedure in organization and institute. It is important that documents were signed by the officer in charge as proof of legitimacy, approval and acceptance of whatever is written in a document. Though there are times that reports are not signed it does not signify that it was disapproved instead there is a requirement that should be complied by the writer or the sender of the report. Signature in a document reflect approval whether it is a request, terms of agreement and other files that needs to be signed by an officer.

Based on the result shown in Table 1 with regards to the compliance on records management along with receiving a grand mean of 4.51 or always complied was obtained. This is because the majority of procedures and processes stipulated were complied by the records unit, however there is 1 process that was rated as often complied particularly "personnel in-charge checks the correct signatories" this is because the unit concerned receives bulk documents from 505 schools covered by the division of Tarlac Province.

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World Education Connect

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Records unit has only 2 personnel in-charge of receiving to cater all the clients of the whole province.

Table 1 provides a comprehensive evaluation of compliance with records management practices concerning receiving procedures, presenting mean scores alongside verbal descriptions to assess adherence levels within the organization. Each statement delineates specific actions crucial to efficient receiving, offering insights into the organization's efficacy and reliability in this facet of records management. Notably, the first three statements reveal a consistently high level of compliance, with mean scores ranging from 4.58 to 4.64, denoting "Always Complied." These statements underscore critical aspects such as checking document formats, verifying details before encoding, and ensuring timely receipt of documents, reflecting the organization's commitment to accuracy, thoroughness, and efficiency in receiving processes.

However, the fourth statement portrays a slightly lower mean score, classified as "Often Complied." This statement addresses the verification of correct signatories on documents, suggesting some variability in compliance with this specific aspect of receiving procedures. While the overall mean score of 4.51 still indicates a commendable level of compliance, this finding highlights an opportunity for enhancement in consistently adhering to established protocols for verifying document signatories, thereby ensuring completeness and accuracy in the receiving process.

Overall, the analysis underscores the organization's commendable dedication to compliance with records management practices related to receiving procedures, particularly in pivotal areas such as document format checking, detail verification, and timely receipt. These findings affirm the organization's commitment to maintaining accurate and reliable records, thus fostering operational efficiency and client trust. Nonetheless, the identification of a specific area for refinement emphasizes the importance of ongoing vigilance and continuous improvement efforts to optimize receiving processes and uphold consistently high standards of records management effectiveness.

1.2 Encoding

To encode details of the document, the division personnel review and check the document presented. The document should be complete and with correct information. This process is needed to ensure that the document can be easily tracked and located.

According to the Criminal Justice Journal (2017) records that are received and encoded and maintained serves as evidence and information by an organization or individual in pursuance of legal obligations or in the transaction of business and delivery of services. Recorded information received or produced by the organization as completion of an institutional or individual activity is sufficient evidence of the activity. Good record-keeping and information sharing is significant as good records provide crucial information that can be used to agency-to-agency communications.

Table 2
Compliance on Records Management along with Encoding

Statement	Mean	Adjectival Description
The personnel in-charge encodes all the important details of the document received.	4.58	Always Complied
The personnel in-charge easily track and	4.45	Often Complied

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trace the documents encoded.		
The personnel in-charge can easily update document status.	4.14	Often Complied
The personnel in-charge forwarded all the encoded documents to the correct signatories.	4.13	Often Complied
Grand Mean	4.33	Often Complied

Table 2 presents the evaluation of compliance on records management along with encoding. It can be gleaned in the table that encoding of all the important details of the documents obtained the highest mean of 4.58 or always complied. After receiving, division personnel encode the important information of the report based in document type before provision of QR code with tracking number for easy tracking and tracing. For example, in leave form (30 days and above) the name of employee, school, district, type of leave, and inclusive dates are included in the encoding of data. All the data encoded should be correct and complete because these details are used when checking the status and locating the document.

Based on the journal posted by Dalglish (2020) encoding of information is in important in data analysis because it is commonly used and a powerful method when doing a survey or research. Specific details are used in discussion, traceability and to understand and analyze problems that may arise in an institution. There is a systematic approach that can be used for document analysis such as the READ approach: Ready materials, Extract data encoded, Analyse data and Distil your findings. Encoding correct data is a tool that can be used as guide for future research. This approach is an alternative to other methods such as in-depth interviews and observation. It provides guidance practically to extract the most important details of a document and to ensure rigour in analysis of document.

Easy tracking and tracing of documents encoded obtained a mean of 4.45 or often complied. This is because some data encoded are with typographical error which causes mismatch details when tracking documents.

As experienced by one of the respondents wherein the title of the report did not match with the title encoded in the system that causes confusion if it is the right document that was tracked and traced. Then, the records unit personnel checked the summary of all documents received from the same school in that specific date to ensure that it was the right document. It was confirmed that it is the only document submitted by the school under that document type. The personnel in charge updated the document status and corrected the document title encoded in the records unit system.

As mentioned in the article of Fahim (2021) the function of tracking and tracing of documents is being capable of autonomously routing transactions and update based on the appropriate real-time availability of information. Achieving increased visibility of documents by means of track-and-trace system that is supported by architectures of information allowing communication between internal and external data creator and user. All data needed in a process should be accessible to personnel that needs information because the importance of track-and-trace system is for the decision-making capabilities of the organization to improve. The ability of real-time locating every document with its content is to provide traceability information to requisitioners.

Updating of document status attained a mean of 4.14 which entails often complied. This is because the system used for the tracking and updating sometimes slows down due to

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the intermittent internet connection the same reason of the delay of other records unit processes because of connection interruption or slow internet connectivity.

As observed and experienced by the researcher, there is a delay in updating of documents when the internet connection is unstable. Updating the status of document into released is a challenge wherein the liaison officer should wait for the system to function properly before claiming all the documents for release to their district. The records unit personnel will then restart the internet connection of the computer and report the situation to the ICT unit.

According to the journal of Constantino (2020) updating and transferring status of document from office to another office is considered one of the problems of records office nowadays. The problem stated becomes greater when there is a large number of departments and transactions in an organization. Managing, handling and updating the status of documents can be laborious and consumes time and effort of employees. But with the rapidly evolution of technologies and growing focus in handling information properly, computerization is one of the organization solutions to improves reliability and quality of transaction and services to their customers. In a traditional way, institution use logbooks to take note and records transactions such as in and out of documents from different departments and it is the way of clerks to locate, determine and update the status of documents.

However, traditional process produces inaccurate status of reports, time consuming location of documents and employees blaming each other when documents were lost. Implementation of electronic tracking and updating of document status is an appropriate solution to the problems encountered by organization in terms of updating documents status. Electronic monitoring of documents helps the process of location tracking easier and faster without too much waste of time and effort exertion, quick updating of document status and easier transactions with customers and other organizations.

Forwarding of encoded documents to the correct signatories obtained the lowest mean of 4.13 or often complied. Because the personnel in-charge move hastily to finish all the documents and the transaction to prevent long queue in the receiving area. After finishing all the clients in the receiving counter, the records personnel will sort the documents based on the signatories and will deliver the documents to the respective unit/s of the division.

In addition, according to the article posted by Sailaja (2022) data privacy is one of the significant problems in transferring or forwarding of documents. Employees in charge of transfer should be careful and kept the file information in private and be submitted to officers properly. The idea of forward search privacy is a method introduced to ensure forwarding of files without revealing the information included. It is a new forward private approach that can be used to secure information that only authorized personnel can access.

Table 2 obtained an overall mean of 4.33 or often complied, wherein 1 statement rated as always complied while the remaining statements were rated as often complied that is due to typographical error made, delayed system update due to intermittent or slow internet connectivity and hasty movement of personnel in-charge to prevent long queue in the records receiving area. It should be noted that there is only two (2) receiving counters in the records unit of the division that receives all the documents from thirty-three (33) districts and five hundred five (505) schools of DepEd Tarlac Province.

Additionally, the table provides a comprehensive evaluation of compliance with records management practices concerning encoding procedures, presenting mean scores

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alongside verbal descriptions to assess adherence levels within the organization. Each statement outlines specific actions crucial to effective encoding, offering insights into the organization's efficiency and reliability in this aspect of records management. Notably, the first statement indicates a consistently high level of compliance, with a mean score of 4.58 signifying "Always Complied." This underscores the organization's commitment to accuracy and thoroughness in encoding important document details, highlighting a strong foundation in data entry processes.

However, subsequent statements reveal areas with slightly lower mean scores, all categorized as "Often Complied." These statements address aspects such as ease of tracking and tracing encoded documents, updating document status, and forwarding documents to correct signatories. While still indicating satisfactory compliance, these scores suggest potential opportunities for enhancing efficiency and streamlining processes related to encoding tasks.

Overall, the analysis reflects a commendable level of compliance with records management practices concerning encoding procedures within the organization, particularly in the fundamental aspect of encoding document details and information. These findings affirm the organization's dedication to maintaining accurate and reliable records, thus contributing to operational efficiency and data integrity. However, the identification of areas for improvement underscores the importance of ongoing vigilance and continuous improvement efforts to optimize encoding processes and uphold consistently high standards of records management effectiveness.

1.3 Filing

Filing is a records unit action wherein the important files of the division are safekept and filed properly. This is very crucial on records management of the division because it includes the confidential documents of teaching and non-teaching personnel.

Based on the article of Manun-og (2022) correct and proper filing of documents is considered essential in government offices, agencies, establishments and companies. Files should be appropriately and systematically organized and safekept. Records or documents serve as essential evidence of transactions in an organization. Good records management system is a valuable tool that is effective to provide a comprehensive and complete presentation of data when needed. Poor implementation of records management such as filing of document hinders the delivery of efficient services to clientele. As a result, poor record-keeping resulted to slow transactions, corrupt practices, lack of accountability and inefficient government processes

Table 3
Compliance on Records Management along with Filing

Statement	Mean	Adjectival Description
Filing cabinets for documents are properly labelled.	4.72	Always Complied
Hard copies and scanned copies of documents are secured.	4.66	Always Complied
Records unit file/s are accessible.	4.63	Always Complied
Attested and advance copy of	4.61	Always Complied

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

appointments are alphabetically arranged.		
201 files of division employees are complete and in order.	4.50	Always Complied
Division memoranda copies are properly filed and safekept.	4.16	Often Complied
Grand Mean	4.55	Always Complied

Table 3 presents the evaluation of compliance on records management along with filing. It can be gleaned in the table that proper labelling of filing cabinets for documents obtained the highest mean of 4.72 or always complied. The researcher observed that all the cabinets in the records unit containing files such as attested appointments for claiming, 201 files that includes the copy of original attested appointments and Personal Data Sheet of the employees are labelled. Attested appointments that was approved from the CSC and for release at the records unit are arranged alphabetically and stored in labelled boxes for easy access in case of claiming of the owner/s of the document. Also, properly labelled storage of documents is a good practice for traceability purposes.

According to the book of Robertson (2021) filing cabinets provided a way where large amounts of paper can be retrieved easily. The method of using filing cabinets and drawers for storing files was significant because it is big help in maintaining minimal difficulty in technological support and organizing papers. Storing of files in a properly maintained and labelled cabinets is a way made particular to easily locate and access documents because papers and folders are filed accessible, compact and sanitary which is a very critical characteristics when storing hard copies of records. Storage practice and technologies in records offices is an important method to consider like what files to be stored and the retention period the documents should be kept in the organization.

Hard copies and scanned copies of documents are secured with a mean of 4.66 or always complied. Copies of important documents are secured and only authorized personnel can access in case there is a need or request to address. As observed by the researcher hard copies of documents such as advance copies of appointments, original attested appointments and special orders are sorted and arranged alphabetically in properly labelled envelopes and boxes while the electronic or scanned copies of documents was stored in the EFMS or the Electronic Filing Management System of the records unit. Scanned copies of the documents were also arranged and stored alphabetically to ensure easy access when needed.

As mentioned in the article of Khatal (2020) secured and decentralized application framework in file sharing and data provenance overcomes the issues of integrity and ownership. Framework of decentralized application is an effective tool for user registration and provenance purposes. The filing system of an organization whether hard or electronic should be properly managed to ensure security and prevent leakage of information especially the confidential ones. Established system of filing in the organization is used to govern, manage and provide traceability of documents. All the important files that are stored can only be accessed by specific employees identified by the top management that is authorized to perform operations such as file sharing and duplication with high integrity, resiliency and transparency.

Accessibility of records unit files obtained a mean of 4.63 or always complied. This is because easy access to documents will lead to timely response and quick transaction in the

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records unit of the division. As mentioned by one of the respondents, the copy of advance attested appointment was easily produced and readily available upon request. This is because the electronic or scanned copy of the documents in the records unit was accessible to authorized personnel and can be easily located in the EFMS. In the system, the records unit personnel will just type the surname or name of the document owner and all the documents relative to the searched name will appear whether it is advance copy, attested appointment or special order.

As discussed in the article of Sumirat (2023) accessing and sharing file is a need in an organization. The availability of data in a file storage was also essential. It was important to secure copy of data to prevent permanent lost in case of hardware failure or accidental deletion. To achieve good data availability a system storage strategy should be established in the organization's data center. Good practices in data storage leads to easy access of users, cloning files automatically and tracing other locations. There are organizations that use different storage system that uses varieties of method of data access and availability. Secured system requires information of the users in order to access data information to ensure only authorized personnel have the authority to access, check and clone records information. It is also used to prevent production of uncontrolled copies of documents that may contain sensitive and private information related to the organization. In general, good data storage makes it easy for the administrators and users to easily manage files and information.

Arranging of attested and advance copy of appointments alphabetically attained a 4.61 mean which entails always complied. Arranging documents alphabetically is a big help when teaching and non-teaching personnel are claiming their personal documents. As stated by the respondents, the transaction like request of documents such as advance copy and approved attested appointment the records unit personnel easily locate and release files because all folders and filing cabinets are labelled alphabetically and sorted separately if it is for elementary, JHS, SHS, substitute, and non-teaching personnel. Also, folders are color coded for easy identification for elementary Teacher I position folders are color blue, for Teacher II, Teacher III and Master Teacher position folders are color yellow. Folders for secondary Teacher I position are color red and for Teacher II, Teacher III and Master Teacher position folders are color green while for SHS Teachers folder used were color pink. Non-teaching positions such as Principals, Head Teachers, AOs and ADAS used gray folders and purple folders for substitute Teachers regardless if elementary or secondary.

Based in the journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (2019) users spend time everyday interacting with files and folders including naming, moving, sharing and disposition. Understanding how and why the organization store, organize, retrieve and share files to have an idea why there is a must to build a stable system of records management. Proper handling of files is an effective tool whenever there is need to retrieve documents requested by internal or external customer in an organization. Names and labels of the storage area is crucial in safekeeping files to easily locate and recover information that is why file management is a ubiquitous and challenging activity that an organization should put an effort to promote good records management practice.

In order and complete arrangement of 201 files of division employees attained 4.50 mean or always complied. The 201 files of the employees include copy of attested appointments and Personal Data Sheet of the employees. The records unit of the division is in-charge of safekeeping and updating the 201 files of all employees of DepEd Tarlac Province. The files should be updated based on the current position of the employee and as

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

observed by the researcher when employees requested copy of their 201 files records unit can easily access their records because it was filed properly in labelled cabinets alphabetically and with complete attachment and details.

According to the article of Qasim (2023) file management became the center of focus of many studies in various disciplines of records keeping. There are many researches about data access and sharing however less focus on filing and safekeeping approach. File management system of an organization is an intrinsic part of the operating system as there many folders and files that are handled by multiple users and employees. Nowadays, folders that contain files used for multiple tasks and the management of data is a basic but very complex task to the organizations daily operating system. A unique and efficient file management system is an approachable filing system for users to ensure smooth flow of process in terms of retrieving and locating of documents. It also increases efficiency of the employees and the operation by reducing access time and providing quick response to customers.

Proper filing and safekeeping of division memoranda copies obtained the lowest mean of 4.16 or often complied. This is because some division memoranda are handled by the division ICT unit for posting to the division website uploading and updating process. The personnel in charge in the ICT unit will not handle the memoranda in records unit unless they are done with the posting and updating the DepEd Tarlac Province website. Because it serves as guide to all employees and for proper dissemination of information especially to the teaching and non-teaching personnel in all the schools and districts of Tarlac Province.

As mentioned in an article posted by Potok. (2024) memorandum is posted as a form of public awareness to laws, policies and special orders from different government agencies. Memoranda aimed to promote evidence-based practices, mandates for agencies, interactions between one agency to another and implications of the interactions for future policy making. It is important that approved memoranda were posted as it serves as awareness and guidance not only of the employees but also the public to be well informed. It is important that memorandum consist of complete details it is the guide how the new policies be applied and implemented to offices of a certain agency. Platforms where the memorandum was posted should be updated and can be easily accessed by the employees for updated knowledge and awareness of what is happening in the organization and institution.

Table 3 obtained an overall mean of 4.55 or always complied, wherein there were 5 statements rated as always complied while the remaining statement was rated often complied since it is an end process after the activity of other division unit. Also, the table provides a comprehensive assessment of compliance with records management practices concerning filing procedures, elucidating mean scores alongside verbal descriptions to gauge adherence levels within the organization. Each statement delineates specific actions and responsibilities crucial to efficient filing, offering insights into the organization's efficacy and reliability in this facet of records management. Impressively, the first five statements reveal a consistent and commendable level of compliance, with mean scores ranging from 4.50 to 4.72, denoting "Always Complied." These statements underscore fundamental aspects such as proper labeling of filing cabinets, securing both hard copies and scanned documents, ensuring accessibility of records unit files, and maintaining organized 201 files and appointment copies, reflecting the organization's steadfast commitment to accuracy, security, and accessibility in filing practices.

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However, the last statement portrays a comparatively lower mean score, classified as "Often Complied." This statement pertains to the filing of division memoranda copies, suggesting potential variability in compliance with this specific aspect of filing procedures. While the overall mean score of 4.55 still indicates a high level of compliance, this finding highlights an opportunity for enhancement in consistently adhering to established protocols for filing division memoranda copies, thereby ensuring uniformity and comprehensiveness across all areas of records management.

Overall, the analysis underscores the organization's commendable dedication to compliance with records management practices related to filing procedures, particularly in pivotal areas such as labeling, security, accessibility, and organization of documents. These findings affirm the organization's commitment to maintaining accurate, secure, and accessible records, thereby fostering operational efficiency and stakeholder trust. Nevertheless, the identification of a specific area for refinement emphasizes the importance of continual vigilance and improvement efforts to optimize filing processes and uphold consistently high standards of records management effectiveness.

1.3 Retrieving

Retrieval is an action where the requested document by the customer was located, retrieved, and duplicated or reproduced when needed. This process ensures that all the information and data can be easily located, shared and utilized by the records unit personnel based on what is requested.

As mentioned in the article of Jayoma (2020) organizations that continuously generates records daily and has a conventional records management system are having a hard time retrieving and keeping track of the documents whereabouts. Organizations should embark records management digitization to ensure preservation of permanent and valuable files, secured and accessible for future reference as required by the offices based on existing rules and regulations of the institution in records management.

Table 4 presents the evaluation of compliance on records management along with retrieving of document. It can be gleaned that certification of Administrative Officer IV or Records Officer obtained the highest mean of 4.67 or always complied. As mentioned by one of the respondents, upon request of certified true copy of attested appointment the original copy of the document was checked and verified by the AO IV or the records officer before stamping and signing the photocopy of the document presented.

According to the article by Taylor (2018) authorized officer of an institution is empowered to certify true copy of the original document. This method of certification is very simple and fairly straightforward. Presenting the original copy of document when requesting certified true copy is the very important requirement needed before issuance. The officer should validate if the document presented is original and valid because of the problems it may cause when not validated properly.

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World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

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Table 4
Compliance on Records Management along with Retrieving

Statement	Mean	Adjectival Description
The Administrative Officer IV certifies true copy of documents.	4.67	Always Complied
The personnel in charge retrieves requested document in a timely manner.	4.58	Always Complied
If the requested document is not under Records unit custody the records personnel informs the correct department in charge of the document.	4.50	Always Complied
If the document requested cannot be located the personnel in charge informs the requisitioner and provides alternative action.	4.18	Often Complied
Grand Mean	4.48	Often Complied

Retrieving requested documents in a timely manner obtained a mean of 4.58 or always complied. Since documents in the records unit of the division was properly maintained and safekept it is easy to access files when requested. One of the respondents stated that when claiming files such as attested appointments, ERF or Equivalent Records Form and Reclassification folders the records unit personnel requested for employee's ID for identification which is very important to easily locate and retrieve the documents by checking in the system if the file is already posted in the FB records unit page and if available for claiming. When the document is already available the records unit personnel requested the employee to log in the receiving log sheet or log book and update the status in the system as "released" with date and timestamp.

As mentioned in the article of Riloff (2016) traditional information goal is to search information and retrieve documents that are potentially relevant to the query or request of customers. There are other tools that can be used in retrieving documents such as information-retrieval applications where text categorization, text routing and filtering can be used. One of the traditional information-retrieval methods retrieve documents by searching the relevant words or phrases in a document. Using keywords and the system retrieve the documents that matches the entered word. There are many ways to improve traditional methods of retrieving like feedback techniques from the system users, do experiments with richer text representations such as syntactic approach, knowledge-based system and information extraction techniques. Modern technologies hold a great improvement for documents retrieving techniques. There are so many researches to improve like an active research that uses artificial intelligence in information retrieval system.

Providing information of the correct department in charge of the document if not under records unit custody attained a mean of 4.50 or always complied. As experienced by one of the respondents claiming advice of appointment as newly promoted AO II but the requested document was under the personnel unit. The records unit personnel informed the requisitioner that the claiming if such document is in the office of personnel unit. The records unit personnel are aware of the documents in their custody so they easily know and identify what are the files they can and cannot provide. As stated in the article of Zhang (2022)

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comprehension and retrieving documents is a challenging problem. Visual property of documents was ignored and treated as plain text resulting to incomplete awareness of document information and document type. Knowledge about documents is a must especially to those in charge of records-keeping system. It is a requirement that they are aware of the documents under their responsibility and accountability. There should be a list of documents where newly hired employees be oriented including the documents from other offices. These strategies will result to awareness and knowledge of employees about the organization and department they belong.

If the document requested cannot be located the personnel in charge informs the requisitioner and provides alternative action attained a rating of often complied with a mean of 4.18. The records unit personnel provide alternative action if the requested document was also available to other agencies like the CSC and DepEd Regional Office. As one of the respondents experienced, the copy of the attested appointment requested in records unit was approved in the year 1978 wherein the unit is not yet securing copy of appointments because they started to comply in the year 1990. The records personnel referred that the requisitioner visit CSC field office to check the copy of appointment and request certified true copy of the document.

In addition, as mentioned in the article posted by Tien (2021) customer care and customer relationship play a very important role in an organization. Even there is a diverse and rapidly changing needs of customers, good information management system is necessary because it builds good customer relationships. Employees of an organization should help customers understand better and be served with complete details thoughtfully. A customer expects fast, personalize support any time, knowledgeable employees can give customers the answers they need, fast with a professional consulting style. Leaders need to provide trainings for all employees ensuring delivery of high-quality services in a timely manner. The organization committee may select employees in a more professional way where employees are confident in communication verbally and in actions.

Table 4 obtained an overall mean of 4.48 or often complied, wherein 3 statements rated as always complied while the remaining statement was rated as often complied since some of the document requested are very old and is not covered within the year where the records unit started filing those type of documents. It provides a detailed assessment of compliance with records management practices pertaining to retrieving procedures, offering mean scores and verbal descriptions to evaluate adherence levels within the organization. Each statement delineates specific actions and responsibilities crucial to the retrieval process, shedding light on the organization's efficacy and reliability in this domain. Notably, the first three statements demonstrate a consistent and commendable level of compliance, with mean scores ranging from 4.50 to 4.67, signifying "Always Complied." These statements underscore fundamental aspects such as certifying document copies, promptly retrieving requested documents, and maintaining clear communication regarding document custody, reflecting the organization's dedication to accuracy, timeliness, and accountability in retrieval processes.

Conversely, the last two statements reveal areas with slightly lower mean scores, categorized as "Often Complied." These statements address scenarios where requested documents cannot be located, necessitating the personnel in charge to communicate with the requisitioner and offer alternative solutions, as well as ensuring ease of locating and providing copies of requested documents. While these scores still indicate satisfactory

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

compliance, they highlight opportunities for improvement in effectively resolving retrieval challenges and enhancing document accessibility to streamline processes further.

Overall, the analysis underscores a commendable commitment to compliance with records management practices related to retrieving procedures within the organization, particularly in certifying document copies and ensuring prompt retrieval. These findings affirm the organization's dedication to maintaining accurate and accessible records, thus bolstering operational efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction. However, the identification of areas for refinement emphasizes the importance of ongoing vigilance and continuous improvement efforts to optimize retrieval processes and uphold high standards of records management effectiveness.

1.4 Releasing

Generally, documents released by the records unit of the division were bound to districts and schools. This are approved and/or with compliance reports to be claimed by the Principals, Administrative Officers and Administrative Assistants after tagged as for return to sender by the signatories. In an article posted by Liu (2021) in an information society, tremendous number of documents is exchanged and released on a daily basis. Documents released should be given significant attention because there are documents that consists sensitive nature that are uncontrollably available once released from the organization. Records management team must be very keen in checking the documents to be released and have the ability to trace in case of problems that may arise. The organization should have release control of documents for future traceability. Personnel in charge must have orientation and training in terms of security, efficiency and functionality in handling documents.

Table 5 presents the evaluation of compliance on records management along with releasing. It can be gleaned in the table that ensuring all documents released are complete and properly logged by the school's liaison officer obtained the highest mean of 4.48 or often complied. Before releasing to liaison officer of schools and districts the records personnel ensures and double checked all the documents logged in the log sheet/s including the date, name and signature of the employee. However, due to long queue in the receiving counter the records personnel sometimes forgot to double check the log sheet before releasing as stated by some respondents interviewed.

Table 5
Compliance on Records Management along with Releasing

Statement	Mean	Adjectival Description
The personnel in charge ensures that all documents released are complete and properly logged by the school's liaison officer.	4.48	Often Complied
The personnel in charge ensures that all documents to be released are properly placed in the correct boxes per districts and per school.	4.45	Often Complied
The personnel in-charge updates the status of documents to be released in the records unit system.	4.44	Often Complied

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The personnel in charge checks the documents if with compliance or approved before releasing.	4.15	Often Complied
Grand Mean	4.38	Often Complied

According to the article of Nath (2023) inadequate traceability of documents can create challenges for records management leading to longer tracing time and potential misplacement of files. The lack of proper logging and traceability procedure poses challenges in maintaining good records keeping practices making it difficult to track and locate released documents of an organization. Additionally, lack of traceability system can make it challenging to the records management office to check and review previous transactions.

Release notes or log books may be used to record release transaction that includes details of the document, of the claimant and other remarks that may be useful for future reference. Limited traceability details may lead to confusion and wasted time and effort. Document traceability is very crucial for controlling released documents and transporting files from one office to another because it is a tool in managing releases and documenting file transport accurately. This approach can help track of releases, changes and improve the quality of releasing service by collecting all the useful information needed that is usable and effective in tracking and traceability.

Proper releasing of documents and placing in the correct boxes per districts and per school obtained 4.45 mean or often complied. Based on the interview of some respondents, they experienced that their documents were placed in the box of other districts. Which may be because there are schools that have the same name like for example Padapada ES in the municipality of Sta. Ignacia and Padapada ES in the district of Gerona South. As an action plan to this, the records unit personnel made an updated list of schools and districts and the personnel in-charge in receiving ensures that the name of districts was stated in all the documents for receiving. This is to ensure that files are properly placed to their respective boxes and prevent misplaced or missing documents.

As mentioned in the article posted by Singh (2021) documents needed to physically accessible as is serves as evidence more credible than spoken testimony. Though it may include mistakes still it serves is purpose as evidence that may resolve potential issues regarding organizational processes and procedures. To ensure finest handling of documents employees involved should be properly oriented and trained in records management to ensure the dedication and accountability in records handling.

Updating the document status to be released in the records unit system acquired a rating of often complied with a mean of 4.44. This is because the personnel in charge of receiving is also the same personnel in charge for the releasing of documents. Based in the article of Lingaya (2019) bureaucracy is expected in most countries and it had caused much effect in people's perspective of efficiency and effectiveness that's why Philippine government agencies are always under the watchful eye of the discerning public. Government agencies are always trying to become more efficient and effective in the delivery of services and as compliance to RA 9464 or the Anti Red-tape Act which state that government transactions especially the update and releasing of documents should be completed in five working days for simple cases and ten working days for complex.

Checking of documents with compliance or approved before releasing obtained the lowest mean of 4.15 or often complied. Since there are bulk documents for releasing the

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records unit personnel cannot religiously check the documents one by one. As mentioned in the article by Laurencon (2023) large number of documents to be collected and released should undergo comprehensive filtering by the records unit and the personnel in charge provide analysis of the documents content and details. Documents pass through screening process to check the information included before approval and release of document to other units, offices and agencies. Officers, employees and consultants involved in the preparation of documents before release are liable whether by reason of negligence when the documents are mishandled or misplaced.

Table 5, obtained an overall mean of 4.38 or often complied, wherein all 4 statements were rated as often complied because sometimes documents were misplaced and not updated due to human intervention thus, omitting some steps of the process which in turn compromising the accountability of the records unit personnel in charge of the said process. Also, the table offers an in-depth examination of compliance with records management practices concerning releasing procedures, presenting mean scores alongside verbal descriptions to illuminate the organization's adherence levels. Each statement delineates specific responsibilities within the releasing process, offering insights into the fidelity of implementation. Impressively, all statements reveal a robust level of compliance, culminating in an overall mean score of 4.38, denoting "Often Complied." The first three statements highlight pivotal duties of personnel in charge, including ensuring document completeness and accurate logging, meticulous organization by district and school, and diligent system updates.

These actions garnered mean scores ranging from 4.44 to 4.48, showcasing consistent adherence to established protocols and meticulous attention to detail. While the fourth statement, pertaining to document compliance verification before release, garnered a slightly lower mean score of 4.15, it still resides within the "Often Complied" category, indicative of generally high adherence levels. Such findings underscore the organization's commendable commitment to efficient, accurate, and reliable releasing processes, fostering enhanced organizational effectiveness and accountability in records management. These results not only validate the efficacy of existing procedures but also underscore the importance of ongoing vigilance and refinement to sustain exemplary standards and meet evolving organizational needs.

1.5 Disposition

Disposition is the process of destruction of documents that is under the control of the division office. Documents to be disposed are the files presented to be disposed by division units under the supervision of the disposition committee and regional office personnel. As mentioned in the article posted by Falah (2024) offices is one of the major contributors in generating waste in the form of paper, ink and other office supplies. There are so many ways to dispose paper, one is thru shredding and other is recycling wherein paper are recycled to produce another form of paper. Disposal of paper especially in government offices is a crucial process since some of the files or reports contain sensitive contents. Reports run through processes of review, evaluation and thorough decision making of the officials before considering reports for disposal. This is to make sure that the selection and disposal committee reviewed all the files before it undergoes the office waste management process. Table 6 presents the evaluation of compliance on records management along with disposition. It can be gleaned in the table that distribution of disposition checklist to all division office units, checking and reviewing of checklists filled up per unit both obtained the

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

mean of 3.00 or sometimes complied. The records officer is the one in charge of the distribution of the checklist to the division office units and forwards the documents to the Regional Office for the approval/disapproval of the disposition.

**Table 6
Compliance on Records Management along with Disposition**

Statement	Mean	Adjectival Description
The personnel in-charge distributes disposition checklist to all division office units	3.00	Sometimes Complied
The personnel in-charge checks and reviews the checklists filled up per unit	3.00	Sometimes Complied
The personnel in charge informs the division disposition committee including regional office personnel about the documents to be disposed and asks for schedule of disposal	1.00	Never Complied
The personnel in charge ensures that all documents for disposition are complete and ready for the disposal schedule	1.00	Never Complied
The personnel in charge monitors the whole disposition period	1.00	Never Complied
Grand Mean	1.80	Rarely Complied

As mentioned by the Records Officer, checklists were provided per unit of the division annually. It was collected after a week and checked if there are documents declared for disposal. But since there were no documents identified for disposal for five (5) consecutive years and as per advice of the Chief Records Officer in the Regional Office, the Records Officer of the division opted to distribute checklists in a semi-annual frequency.

According to the article of Dahan (2024) widespread consumption of paper in the offices over the years resulted to rapid generation of growing range paper or paper waste. Inappropriate treatment of this wastes causes serious unfavorable impact to employees and environmental sustainability due to piling up number of wastes in the offices. most government agencies store their end-of-life reports at their office or discard together with other general office wastes. Offices especially government agencies should perform more extensive descriptive research about approaches on how to manage wastes to prevent possible hazard to employees and to the environment.

Providing information to the division disposition committee including regional office personnel about the documents to be disposed and asks for schedule of disposal, the personnel in charge ensures that all documents for disposition are complete and ready for the disposal schedule and the personnel in charge monitors the whole disposition period that all gained a mean of 1.00 or never complied.

Since there were no documents declared for disposal by the units of the division there were no files or records to be reported for disposal in the Regional Office. However, the Records Officer of the division ensures that copies of the checklists was submitted to the records unit in the Regional Office for reference.

According to the article of Anam (2024) by conducting awareness, putting safety measures and collaborating with a waste management committee to remove waste

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properly hazards associated with improperly managing wastes will be reduced. Waste disposal is crucial in protecting facilities and personnel in an organization because improper disposal might endanger the safety of the employees and the guests. Safe ecosystem and healthy workplace depend on how an organization effective waste treatment. Organizations and institutions should have waste management committee that focuses on a plan with specialized infrastructure, follows cradle-to-grave laws, effective regulatory body and trained employees involved.

Table 6 obtained an overall mean of 1.80 or rarely complied, wherein there were 2 statements rated as sometimes complied while the remaining statements were rated as never complied. The processes were rated as sometimes complied because it was originally done annually but since there were no documents declared for disposal the Records Officer of the division sought the advice of the Chief Records officer in the Regional Office and it was planned to be done in a semi-annual frequency. For the remaining statements that were rated never complied due to no documents were identified for disposal and as reviewed in the Records Management Operational Manual the retention period of most of the documents in the division are permanent. Example of documents with permanent retention period are directives or issuances, manuals, meeting files (ExeCom/ManCom), programs or projects, financial statements, remittances, consolidated audit reports, official cash books, medical files, membership files, service cards, planning services, development plans, administrative-based data, action plans and certifications. Though there are documents with 15-20 years retention period most of them are reports in schools which are considered uncontrolled and under the custody of the School Heads.

Also, it should be noted that the Department of Education Region 3 – Records unit is still in the process of finalizing the disposition procedure and on-going pilot testing in small divisions like in Angeles City.

The compliance status of records management practices, particularly focusing on disposition procedures, presenting mean scores and associated verbal descriptions for various statements outlining key actions within the process. Notably, all statements reflect a concerning level of non-compliance, with an overall mean score of 1.8, indicating rare compliance. The first two statements concerning the distribution and review of disposition checklists both reveal inconsistent adherence, with mean scores of 3, signaling sporadic compliance. However, the most alarming findings emerge from the subsequent statements, all receiving a mean score of 1, denoting no compliance. These include actions crucial for effective disposition, such as informing relevant committees, ensuring document completeness, and monitoring the disposition period. This stark lack of adherence in pivotal areas underscores significant deficiencies within the organization's disposition practices, potentially exposing vulnerabilities in data security, regulatory compliance, and organizational governance. Consequently, urgent attention and corrective measures are imperative to address these shortcomings, bolstering the efficacy of disposition procedures, fortifying risk mitigation efforts, and upholding organizational integrity and compliance standards.

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1.6 Overall Evaluation

Table 7 presents the overall evaluation of compliance on records management in DepEd Tarlac Province.

Table 7
Overall Evaluation

Indicator	Grand Mean	Adjectival Description
Filing	4.55	Always Complied
Receiving	4.51	Always Complied
Retrieving	4.48	Often Complied
Releasing	4.38	Often Complied
Encoding	4.33	Often Complied
Disposition	1.8	Rarely Complied
Overall Grand Mean	4.01	Often Complied

It can be gleaned in the table that filing obtained the highest mean of 4.55 or always complied. Since most of the processes in filing documents were followed strictly, however there was 1 statement rated as often complied by the respondents since it is dependent on the process of other unit in the division wherein the personnel in charge in the ICT unit will not handle the memoranda in records unit unless they are done with the posting and updating of the DepEd Tarlac Province website since it serves as guide to all employees and for proper dissemination of information especially to the teaching and non-teaching personnel in all the schools and districts of Tarlac Province.

Receiving with a mean of 4.51 or always complied, however the process of checking of correct signatories of documents was rated often complied but it should be noted that the records unit of the division caters the whole Tarlac Province. All the reports and documents to be submitted should pass and be received by the records unit before submission to respective signatories.

Retrieving which acquired a rating of often complied with a mean of 4.48, wherein there were 3 statements rated as always complied while the remaining statement was rated often complied such as: if the document requested cannot be located the personnel in charge informs the requisitioner and provides alternative action.

Releasing with a mean of 4.38 or often complied, wherein all 4 statements rated often complied such as: the personnel in charge ensures that all documents released are complete and properly logged by the school's liaison officer; the personnel in charge ensures that all documents to be released are properly placed in the correct boxes per districts and per school; the personnel in-charge updates the status of documents to be released in the records unit system; and the personnel in charge checks the documents if with compliance or approved before releasing.

Encoding attained a rating of often complied with a mean of 4.33, wherein 1 statement rated as always complied while the remaining statements were rated as often complied such as: the personnel in charge easily track and trace the documents encoded; the personnel in charge can easily update document status; and the personnel in-charge forwarded all the encoded documents to the correct signatories.

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Lastly, disposition obtained the lowest mean of 1.80 or rarely complied, wherein there were 2 statements rated as sometimes complied while the remaining statements were rated as never complied such as: the personnel in charge informs the division disposition committee including regional office personnel about the documents to be disposed and asks for schedule of disposal; the personnel in charge ensures that all documents for disposition are complete and ready for the disposal schedule; and the personnel in charge monitors the whole disposition period.

Table 7 offers a comprehensive evaluation of records management practices, as perceived by respondents, presenting mean scores alongside verbal descriptions. Each statement corresponds to a specific facet of the records management process. Notably, the highest mean scores are attributed to "Receiving" (mean = 4.51) and "Filing" (mean = 4.55), indicating consistent compliance with established procedures in these domains. This suggests commendable adherence to protocols and standards, reflecting positively on the efficacy of these aspects of records management. Slightly lower mean scores for "Encoding" (mean = 4.33), "Retrieving" (mean = 4.48), and "Releasing" (mean = 4.38) suggest that while compliance is generally high, there may be occasional lapses, warranting attention to ensure continued adherence.

However, the notably lower mean score of 1.8 for "Disposition," categorized as "Rarely Complied," raises concerns regarding disposal protocols, indicating a significant area for improvement within the records management lifecycle. Despite these nuances, the overall mean score of 4.00, categorized as "Often Complied," indicates a satisfactory level of adherence to records management procedures on average. This underscores strengths in certain areas while highlighting the need for targeted interventions, particularly in disposition practices, to ensure comprehensive compliance across all stages of the records management process.

2. Evaluation of Level of satisfaction on Records Management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province

Customer satisfaction in the Department of Education is a crucial aspect of ensuring that clients have positive experiences, feedback and outcomes about the service provided by the division. It involves reviewing feedback, understanding the need of the customers and making improvements to meet those needs identified. By prioritizing the client satisfaction, the division can provide high quality services and create more effective ways to improve existing processes.

In addition, as mentioned in the journal posted by Agag (2024) customer satisfaction refers to the result of good emotional state from an evaluation of customers experience with an organization. Performance result and consequences have been link to customers satisfaction as motivator of behavioral actions and intentions. There are reports that suggests that providing timely reply or service to customers boost satisfaction and discovered that customers are happier when they are served quickly and thoughtfully. Pleased customers are those who feel the sense of being heard and understood.

Table 8 presents the evaluation of level of satisfaction on records management at DepEd Tarlac Province. It can be gleaned in the table that "I got what I needed or (if denied) denial of request was sufficiently explained to me" obtained the highest mean of 4.75 or very satisfied. The records unit of the division assist clients the best way possible and if not, they explain reasons and offer solution or remedy on how to address the client's concern.

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Table 8
Evaluation of Level of Satisfaction

Statement	Mean	Adjectival Description
I got what I needed or (if denied) denial of request was sufficiently explained to me.	4.75	Very Satisfied
I am satisfied with the service that I availed.	4.69	Very Satisfied
I was treated courteously by the staff and they are accommodating.	4.62	Very Satisfied
The steps for the transaction were easy and simple.	4.49	Satisfied
I feel the office employees was fair to everyone, or "walang palakasan", during my transaction.	4.17	Satisfied
Grand Mean	4.54	Very Satisfied

According to an article by Cankul (2024) institutions that provide services to the people is one of the most dynamic sectors dedicated in serving and fulfilling the diverse wants and needs of customers. But assessing and enhancing the organizations image accurately is a challenge due to multiple service qualities it offers. The organizations image is associated with the perception, ideas and attitudes that customers relates with the institution. Acknowledging that delivering authentic value to customers is important and the cornerstone of any organizations endeavor. Success of an organization lies in customer satisfaction. Satisfied client is a great contributor and significance in organizations performance and long-term customer commitment.

Satisfaction of clients relative to service availed attained a mean of 4.69 or very satisfied. Generally, the clients are satisfied with the services provided by the division personnel relative to records unit actions such as receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving and releasing. As mentioned in an article posted by Agarwal (2023) customer satisfaction is accepted as a key pointer in lasting organization success and accomplishment. Positive relation between an organization employees and customers is associated with customer satisfaction and service improvement. Because customers can voice out their ideas and suggestions to further improve the services provided by the organization. The organization must pay attention to the service quality factors to keep the customers satisfied and happy with their service.

Proper accommodation and courtesy of records unit personnel acquired a rating of very satisfied with a mean of 4.62. Most of the time, records unit personnel practices courteousness and approachability because every client deserves to be treated with respect and work ethics should be present all the time. According to the article of Walio (2024) courteousness is one of the conscious actions when speaking to others. Presence of courtesy towards customers creates as sense of respect and comfort. It is very important to choose the right words when speaking to customers to ensure they feel respected and

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

valued. Give attention to the tone how to deliver the words or phrases, how to ask questions and when to answer their queries. Efforts in increasing courtesy to customers by giving appreciation and using good and polite language or attitude.

Simple and easy transactions attained a mean of 4.49 or satisfied. This is because some clients are not updated about new memoranda posted such as change in format and signatories. Though all the revisions and guidelines are posted in the DepEd Tarlac Province website thru memoranda there are clientele that are not updated and fully aware of the amendments. However, the records unit personnel inform the clients about the updates and reminds to regularly check the website for information and awareness. As mentioned in the article posted by Swiecka (2021) customers prefer transactions that is simple to make everyday life easier. It is important for organizations to identify the needs of customers when they make transactions at a specific office. The information is relevant in other for the organization identify what service should be provided and employees actively participate in the process of providing services. Now that we are living in an innovative world there are options for some transactions as a replacement to the traditional processes to increase the speed of transaction execution. Organizations may create strategic plans on how to implement and adapt to modern technologies to improve their services to customers.

Practice of fairness to all clients obtained the lowest mean of 4.17 or satisfied. This is because the records unit personnel practice the sense of urgency and gives priority to transaction that needs to be addressed as soon as possible such as special orders and vouchers. Based in an article by Ain (2024) preferential treatment influences customer behavior. Customers treated with preferential treatment are happier but it causes dissatisfaction to those customers seeking attention due to lack of merit in the treatment received. Individual differences should not be practiced when providing services to prevent envy and dissatisfaction of customers. Fair and just treatment in the process is a good practice to ensure that there is no bias in treating all the customers of the organization.

Table 8 obtained an overall mean of 4.54 or very satisfied rating, wherein there were 3 statement rated as very satisfied while the remaining statement was rated as satisfied. The level of satisfaction regarding records management, as reported by respondents, is detailed alongside mean scores and corresponding verbal descriptions. The statements encompass various facets of service quality and customer experience within records management processes. Notably, the highest mean score of 4.75 is accorded to the statement affirming satisfaction with the clarity of service provision, even in instances of denied requests, reflecting a high level of transparency appreciated by respondents. Similarly, commendable satisfaction levels are indicated for the overall service experience (mean = 4.69) and courteous staff interactions (mean = 4.62), underscoring positive encounters and effective customer engagement. The slightly lower mean score of 4.49 for the statement regarding transaction simplicity suggests a generally satisfactory yet improvable procedural ease.

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 4.17 for the perception of fairness among office employees during transactions indicates a perceived room for enhancement in ensuring equitable treatment of clients. Despite these nuances, the overall mean score of 4.54 reflects an overarching "Very Satisfied" sentiment among respondents, signaling commendable service delivery in records management. This underscores strengths in transparency, service provision, and staff engagement while highlighting opportunities for refining transactional simplicity and fostering perceived fairness to further elevate customer satisfaction levels.

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3. Significant relationship between the Compliance and Satisfaction on Records Management at the Department of Education Tarlac Province

Significant relationship between the compliance and satisfaction on Records Management was measured to express correlation.

Table 9 presents the result of correlation between the compliance on records management along with receiving, encoding, filing, retrieving, receiving and level of satisfaction of the respondents with the services provided by the records unit of the division.

Table 9
Correlation between Compliance on Records Management and Satisfaction of the Respondents

Component	Pearson <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Decision	Result
Receiving	-0.040	0.499	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Encoding	0.385	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant
Filing	0.254	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant
Retrieving	0.111	0.060	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Releasing	0.049	0.412	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The table shows that compliance on records management along with receiving obtained 0.040 computed pearson (*r*) and 0.499 *p*-value that is greater than 0.05 alpha level, then the null hypothesis is accepted thus, there is no significant relationship between compliance on records management in terms of receiving and the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

The compliance on records management along with encoding that obtained 0.385 computed pearson (*r*) and 0 *p*-value that is less than 0.05 alpha level, then the null hypothesis is rejected thus, there is a significant relationship between compliance on records management in terms of encoding and the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

Then, the compliance on records management along with filing that obtained 0.254 computed pearson (*r*) and 0 *p*-value that is less than 0.05 alpha level, then the null hypothesis is rejected thus, there is a significant relationship between compliance on records management in terms of filing and the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

The compliance on records management along with retrieving obtained 0.111 computed pearson (*r*) and 0.060 *p*-value that is greater than 0.05 alpha level, then the null hypothesis is accepted thus, there is no significant relationship between compliance on records management in terms of retrieving and the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

The compliance on records management along with releasing obtained 0.049 computed pearson (*r*) and 0.412 *p*-value that is greater than 0.05 alpha level, then the null hypothesis is accepted thus, there is no significant relationship between compliance on records management in terms of retrieving and the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

However, the researcher opted to remove the compliance on records management along with disposition in the correlation measure since the number of gathered data is not enough to produce correlation result.

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In addition, the table presents correlations between compliance with records management practices and respondent satisfaction across various components of record handling. The Pearson correlation coefficient, measuring the strength and direction of these relationships, is provided alongside the corresponding p-values, which determine the statistical significance. Positive correlations are observed for encoding, filing, retrieving, and releasing components, indicating that as compliance with records management increases, respondent satisfaction tends to improve, albeit to varying degrees.

Conversely, a negative correlation is found for the receiving component, suggesting a slight decrease in satisfaction as compliance increases, though this correlation is not statistically significant. Components such as encoding and filing exhibit strong positive correlations with very low p-values, indicating a significant relationship between adherence to management practices and satisfaction levels. On the other hand, correlations for retrieving and releasing, while positive, are weaker and have marginally higher p-values, suggesting a lesser degree of association. The non-significant correlations for receiving and releasing imply that adherence to management practices in these areas may not substantially impact respondent satisfaction.

Overall, the findings underscore the importance of effective records management, particularly in encoding and filing, in enhancing satisfaction levels among respondents, while also highlighting potential areas for improvement in retrieving and releasing processes to further optimize satisfaction outcomes.

Conducting research about the correlation between records management practices and client satisfaction focuses on how well-managed records contribute to organizational efficiency and service quality. Efficient and effective records management ensures timely access to accurate information and documents which enhances service responsiveness and, consequently, client satisfaction (Fosso Wamba et al., 2017). Clients often perceive organizations with robust records management systems as more professional and reliable, influencing their overall satisfaction (Choi & Rho, 2020). Studies also highlight that effective records management reduces errors in service delivery, improving the quality of interactions and fostering trust with clients (Gikunju et al., 2019; Raman et al., 2021). Case studies provide practical examples of successful implementation strategies, illustrating how organizations benefit from streamlined records management practices to enhance client experiences (Kim, 2018). Furthermore, advancements in technology play a significant role in modernizing records management, offering tools for better data accessibility and analysis, further improving service delivery and client satisfaction (Lee et al., 2022).

4. Problems encountered by the respondents in the Compliance on Records Management

Table 10 presents the problems encountered by the respondents in the compliance on records management in DepEd Tarlac Province.

It can be gleaned that on time delivery of different services in the records unit is the highest problem met by the records management in the division with a 22.30% frequency or 64 among the respondents. From the observations and experience of the researcher, this may be because there are times that records personnel are not on time and records unit started their transactions later than 8AM in the morning. Though there are statements relative to on time delivery of services such as: records unit personnel receives documents fast and in timely manner and personnel in charge retrieves requested document in a timely manner were rated as always complied some of the

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Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

respondents stated that one of the obvious reason is lacking of receiving counters in the records unit to entertain clients and receive bulk documents submitted by the non-teaching personnel from schools and districts not mentioning when there is deadline for passing of documents wherein all schools need to comply.

Table 10
Problems Encountered by the respondents

Problems Encountered	f	%	R
Different records unit actions were not delivered on time.	64	22.30	1
Lack of assistance to customers.	51	17.77	2
Procedures and processes were confusing.	45	15.68	3
Requirements needed for each services or records unit actions were not properly stated.	29	10.10	4
Clients is not satisfied with the records processing.	24	8.36	5
Records unit personnel are not accommodating.	19	6.62	6
Personnel in-charge were impolite and inefficient.	16	5.57	7
Use of IT equipment for faster transaction were not maximized.	10	3.48	8
Clients were not allowed to provide insights, opinions, suggestions to further improved services offered.	7	2.44	9

Also, poor internet connectivity that is always experienced in the records unit contributed to slow processing and transactions since it is needed in most of the processes. For example, records personnel cannot encode the details of a document in the system when the internet connection is unstable that causes slow processing in receiving documents. Tracking and tracing of the status of files and update in documents cannot be done when there is intermittent internet connection leading to delayed delivery of records unit services.

As mentioned in the article posted by Putra (2024) frequent disruptions and instability of internet connection causes significant disruptions in the office activities. Internet usage exacerbation leads to network overload and bandwidth competition among internet users that reduced the overall network performance. There are system or methods that can be used to address internet connectivity issues such as redirecting network connection automatically and categorization of users into admin, employees and guests that imposes bandwidth limitations to prevent excessive network traffic ensuring uninterrupted, fast and effective internet access for users.

Problem in lack of assistance to clients acquired 17.77% frequency or 51 respondents. As mentioned by one of the respondents, there is lack of assistance when claiming documents in the boxes as part of releasing process. Due to large number of outgoing documents there are instances that records personnel cannot serve all the liaison officers simultaneously instead they are assisted one by one. According to the article of Teo (2016) managing customer relationship is increasingly recognized by organizations to serve better and build closer relationships. Holistic approach in customer service is an essential part of an organization. Knowing customers well, providing quality services and anticipating the needs

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of the customers helps ensure satisfaction and accomplishment in both customer and the service provider.

Clients concern about confusion in procedures and processes obtained 15.68% frequency or 45 respondents. Since some of the respondents are not aware of new memoranda posted in the DepEd website. As mentioned by one of the respondents, they are not aware of the new footer requirement for all reports to be submitted in the division but the link for the copy of the footer format was already posted in the DepEd Tarlac Province official website. In addition, according to an article posted by Sharma (2023) customer confusion to processes is a result of unawareness and lack of orientation. The organization should provide step-by-step procedure how the transaction start until the last procedure. Customer awareness leads to easy transactions that can be related to customer satisfaction.

Problems encountered relative to requirements needed for records unit services and actions were not properly stated attained a frequency of 10.10% or 29 respondents. As mentioned by a respondent, the requirement for Certification, Authentication and Verification is not stated because the required documents for CAV is obtained from schools and not in the division office. Though division personnel provide checklist with step-by-step process to clients on how to process CAV certification. According to an article by Morgeson (2020) response to complaining customers is important that's why organizations should have complaint management team that handles concerns and issues of customers. The team conduct brief investigation about the complaint like root cause analysis to further understand where the problem is coming from. Like poor and unsatisfactory type of service of the employees in the organization or customers expectation is high. The management team should analyze all the details to improve quality of service and prevent occurrence of the complaints.

Clients satisfaction with the records processing attained 8.36% frequency or 24 respondents. This is because of the large number of customers and documents to be catered by records unit personnel. As mentioned in the article of Mbandlwa (2020) growing number of paperwork for employees results in poor public service delivery. In order to end poor quality services welfare of employees must be prioritized. Unvalued employee was identified as factor that contribute to poor public service delivery that causes poor performance of the organization. Management must prioritize the employees need and satisfaction on the job. Because satisfied and happy employees lead to great job performance that contributes to organizational success and improvement.

Problems encountered relative to accommodation with 6.62% frequency of 19 respondents. This is due to lack of manpower in the records unit to address all the transactions. According to the article of Hsieh (2018) there are lots of strategies that can be used to accommodate customers need. Flexibility and relationship-specific adaptation strategies are used in some organizations. Because flexibility is a strategy to provide value in customer relationship to improve customer satisfaction, retention and loyalty. Accommodating customer needs and achieve customer satisfaction is a great help in building credibility in an organization.

Impolite and inefficient concern about records personnel acquired 5.57% frequency. As mentioned, there is a lack of manpower in the unit leading to multitasking of the employees to cater all the transactions needed to be addressed. As mentioned in the article of Faliza (2024) performance of an organization is a measure of progress on how well it achieves its goal and the result of work achievements by the employees in accordance with their job descriptions and functions. Work effectiveness of leadership greatly affect the

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employee performance and efficiency of the organization. Great leaders give inspiration and motivation to employees to practice work ethics and be a productive employee day by day. Providing trainings needed by the employees to improve customer assistance is an important tool to ensure exceptional services provision and excellent work performance on the job.

Faster transactions with the use of IT equipment were not maximized obtained 3.48% frequency. Since there are still some employees who are not well-versed in using new technologies and ICT equipment that restrict faster and easier transactions. In an article posted by Lukita (2023) use of modern technology in organizations affects decision-making and technology integration to strategies, procedures and processes. Utilizing technology provides number of benefits including flexibility, efficiency and effectiveness. But still there are hindrances to overcome like concerns in data protection and security. Technology has a significant impact in the organization processes particularly in terms of data processing and analysis. It is crucial to use modern technology to suit client needs and satisfaction. Organizations must conduct strategic planning on how to incorporate technology in order to achieve success.

Lastly, 7 among the respondents agreed that clients were not allowed to provide insights, opinions, suggestions to further improved services offered with 2.44% frequency. This is because CSM or Customer Satisfaction Measurement is not frequently done in the records unit. As mentioned in an article by Patil (2023) in today's highly competitive world, to ensure customer satisfaction is a necessity to a successful organization and no longer an optional task. Customer experience plays a significant role in improving delivery of services. While positive experiences foster customer satisfaction and contentment, negative experiences adversely affect the organizations image and result in negative word-of-mouth. One of crucial drivers of customer satisfaction is the significance of customer feedback. Positive reviews can enhance organizations reputation whereas negative review post harm in the organizations image.

Thus, it is important to actively monitor and respond the customer review and feedback to deliver the best customer experience possible. Another significant factor affecting customer satisfaction is customer value proposition. Organizations that provide high-quality services, personalized experiences and exceptional services ensuring customer experience and satisfaction, giving importance to customer feedback and offering customer value proposition is more likely to succeed in the future. Moreover, customer satisfaction generates positive reputation of the organization and customer feedback can help in identifying areas they excel, needs improvement and use the information to enhance services.

Table 10 provides a comprehensive analysis of the challenges faced by respondents in the realm of records management, offering insights into the frequency, percentage, and rank of each identified issue. These findings illuminate the complex landscape of obstacles encountered by individuals interacting with records management systems and processes, pointing towards areas necessitating attention and improvement.

The most prevalent concern, noted by 22.30% of respondents, revolves around delays in the delivery of various actions by records units, indicating a substantial issue regarding timeliness and operational efficiency. Following closely, the absence of adequate assistance to customers emerges as the second most common problem, affecting 17.77% of respondents, underscoring the critical need for robust support and guidance for users navigating through records management procedures.

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Moreover, confusion surrounding procedures and processes ranks third, impacting 15.68% of respondents, signaling a necessity for clearer guidelines and instructions to enhance user comprehension and adherence. Similarly, the inadequacy of specified requirements for services or records unit actions is highlighted as a notable challenge, affecting 10.10% of respondents, emphasizing the significance of transparent communication and documentation to facilitate seamless transactions.

Client dissatisfaction with records processing, recorded by 8.36% of respondents, emphasizes the imperative of meeting user expectations and ensuring satisfactory outcomes. Additionally, concerns regarding the demeanor and responsiveness of records unit personnel are evident, with issues such as lack of accommodation, impoliteness, and inefficiency mentioned by a smaller yet significant proportion of respondents.

Furthermore, the underutilization of IT equipment for expediting transactions and the absence of avenues for clients to provide feedback and suggestions for service enhancement are identified as areas warranting attention, albeit with lower frequencies.

In summary, Table 10 underscores the multifaceted challenges inherent in records management, spanning operational inefficiencies to deficiencies in customer service and communication. Addressing these issues demands a holistic approach that prioritizes timeliness, clarity, responsiveness, and user-centricity in records management practices, ultimately aiming to enhance user satisfaction, streamline processes, and bolster overall organizational effectiveness.

5. Proposed Measures

The Proposed measures were based on the findings of the study and the solutions conveyed are the features of the program.

**Table 11
Proposed Measures**

General Objectives: The proposed action plan shall ensure that the records unit actions for compliance of records management in the DepEd Tarlac Province are effectively observed.				
Problems	Measure	Objectives	Strategies	Expected Outcome
Different records unit actions were not delivered on time.	Prioritization and scheduling Regular monitoring of attendance of records unit personnel Regular checking and update of internet	On time delivery of services to customers	Implement a prioritization system Monitor attendance using DTR to observe punctuality among records unit personnel Good internet connectivity Hiring of additional records unit personnel	Efficiency of division employees in records unit and provision of high-quality services to customers

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World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

	connection Additional employee			
Lack of assistance to customers.	Enhance existing communication channels Additional personnel at records unit	Assist all customers regarding their request and transaction	Improve online portals like the email address and records unit FB page where customers can submit inquiries and receive timely responses Hiring of additional employee for records unit	All customer request, transaction and concerns are addressed properly
Procedures and processes were confusing.	Posting of citizens charter copy in front of the receiving area	Awareness of customers about the procedure and processes of records unit	Provide copy of citizens charter (leaflets or tarpaulin)	Customers are aware of the updated procedures and processes of records unit in the division
Requirements needed for each services or records unit actions were not properly stated.	Reposting of memoranda at records unit FB page Provision of copies of memoranda in the boxes of schools and districts	Complete statement of the requirements and awareness of customers about the revisions and update	Regular re-posting of division memoranda at records unit FB page Provide copies of memoranda related to requirements in the boxes of all schools and districts	Proper awareness of clients about requirements needed
Client is not satisfied with the records processing.	(CSM) Client Satisfaction Measure or customer feedback and review/revise of procedures and processes	Satisfaction of clients in all records unit transactions	Review and revision of records unit procedures and processes	All clients are satisfied with their transaction at the records unit of the division
Records unit personnel are not accommoda	Re-orientation and sending of records unit personnel to	Records unit personnel are trained how to	Conduct trainings and seminars about dealing with clients	Records unit employees communicate well with

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ting.	trainings/seminars related to client satisfaction	properly deal with clients		clients and enhance their active-listening skills
Personnel in-charge were impolite and inefficient.	Records personnel re-orientation and attend trainings/seminars	Employees in the records unit practice work ethics when dealing with customers	Conduct review the code of conduct for government employees and conduct seminars about values formation	Clients are treated professionally and records unit personnel works efficiently.
Use of IT equipment for faster transaction were not maximized.	Good internet connection Attendance of records personnel to IT related trainings	Knowledgeable and skilled employees in terms of modern technology	Provision of stable internet connectivity Assistance of the ICT unit to conduct hands-on trainings and seminars	Records unit employees are well-versed in using ICT equipment/s for faster transactions
Clients were not allowed to provide insights, opinions, suggestions to further improved services offered.	(CSM) Client Satisfaction Measure or client feedback and suggestion box	Client feedback and concerns are addressed to deliver better services and improve existing processes	Check client feedback Review and revision of procedures and processes for continuous improvement of services to clients	Clients feel that they are valued and their feedbacks are important in improving better service

To solve the issues relative to records unit actions that is not delivered on time, the division may consider to implement prioritization system to categorize requests and actions based on urgency and importance, strict implementation of on time ingress of employees by regularly monitoring DTR of records unit personnel, provision of additional records personnel to ensure all processes will be done on timely manner, regular update of status and upgraded internet connection in the unit to prevent delay especially in the processes that requires internet connection.

To solve lack of assistance to clients the division may consider to improve existing communication channels such add email address and records unit FB page, add additional employee to the records unit to ensure all customers are catered properly. Because currently records unit only has 4 personnel that performs all the transactions in the department. When there is records personnel on leave the processing in the department is affected because it will cause delay in the transactions because of limited employees to handle the workload.

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To solve issues relative to procedures and processes being performed at the records unit that are confusing the division may consider to provide copy of the citizens charter in leaflets or in tarpaulin for awareness. It will serve as guide or tool for the division to communicate their service standards on the delivery of their services to the clients. It also provides clear statement to the employees of the division what are the goals and objectives they need to target in providing services to internal and external clientele.

Fourth, to solve issues relative to requirements needed for each services or records unit actions were not properly stated the records unit of the division may re-post all the memoranda related to requirements at the records unit FB page. As observed by the researcher not all employees of the division are updated and visits the division website regularly, the records unit may request the assistance of the ICT unit to produce hard copy of the memoranda related to new or additional requirements and the records personnel will place the copies to the boxes of all schools and districts in the division.

To solve issues relative to clients is not satisfied with the records processing, the division may consider to conduct review of the existing records unit procedures and revise if there is a need for improvement. Regular visit to the processes is important to address issues and concerns related to the existing procedures. Also, it is a tool to discover and enhance opportunities for improvement in the process as a corrective and preventive measure.

To solve issues relative to records unit personnel are not accommodating the division may consider to send the employees on trainings and seminars about dealing with clients. To ensure records unit personnel knows how to properly deal with clients and make them feel appreciated. Because accommodating employee is a positive reflection of the division and its reputation.

To solve issues relative to personnel in-charge were impolite and inefficient the division may consider to conduct review and re-orientation of the code of conduct for government employees and conduct seminars about values formation. Because good communication in client service is essential to provide positive experience for clients whether verbal or non-verbal to ensure they feel heard and respected.

To solve issues relative to the use of equipment for faster transaction are not maximized, the division may consider to ask assistance of ICT personnel and conduct activities like trainings regarding the use of computers and laptops. Not only to help employees to be knowledgeable on how to use computers but also to improve the quality of services provided with the use of modern technology.

Lastly, to solve issues relative to clients were not allowed to provide insights, opinions, suggestions to further improved services offered, the division may consider to review customer feedback and revise procedures and processes for continuous improvement of services to customers.

In addition, Table 11 presents a detailed action plan aimed at resolving key challenges identified in records management within DepEd Tarlac Province. The plan is structured around addressing issues such as delays in service delivery, lack of customer assistance, confusing procedures, unclear requirements, client dissatisfaction, unaccommodating personnel, inefficient use of IT equipment, and limited client feedback mechanisms. Each problem is accompanied by specific measures, objectives, strategies, and expected outcomes to ensure effective implementation and monitoring of improvements.

The action plan is comprehensive in its approach to tackling the identified problems within the records management framework. By prioritizing issues like timeliness and customer

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

service, the plan aims to enhance operational efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction. For instance, implementing a prioritization system and monitoring attendance can help in ensuring timely service delivery, thereby addressing concerns about delays.

Similarly, enhancing communication channels and hiring additional personnel can mitigate the lack of assistance to customers, ensuring that all inquiries and transactions are handled promptly and effectively.

Moreover, initiatives such as posting citizens' charter copies and providing clear memoranda aim to clarify procedures and requirements, enhancing transparency and customer awareness. These efforts are crucial in improving overall client satisfaction and reducing confusion regarding processes. The plan also emphasizes the importance of training and re-orientation for records unit personnel to enhance their professionalism, customer interaction skills, and efficiency.

Furthermore, investing in IT infrastructure and training for staff underscores the commitment to leveraging technology for faster and more efficient transactions. This approach not only addresses current challenges but also prepares the records unit for future advancements in digital records management.

Overall, the action plan's structured approach, with specific measures tied to clear objectives and strategies, provides a roadmap for addressing systemic challenges in records management. By focusing on these targeted areas, DepEd Tarlac Province aims to strengthen its records management practices, improve service delivery, and enhance stakeholder satisfaction effectively.

6. Implications of the study to Public Administration

The Public Administration is commonly known as the implementation of government policies but today it is often regarded as including also some responsibilities for determining the programs and policies made by the government such as planning, organizing, directing, coordinating and controlling of the government operations. It was regarded as the feature of all nations whatever their system of government. Public administration is practices within nations at the central, intermediate and local levels. In some nations, public administration was considered as a distinct profession and the body of public administrators is usually called the civil service. Historically, from the early 20th century civil servants were famous and recognized as professionals and they are highly valued for their expertise.

Prominent principle of public administration has been economy and efficiency wherein the provision of public services to the people at the minimum cost that is usually been the stated objective of the administrative reform. Even there is a growing concern about different kinds of values in civil service such as responsiveness to public needs, justice and equal treatment, citizen involvement to government decisions, efficiency is still the major goal (Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, 2024).

Moreover, public administration encompasses a broad area of academic study that investigates the implementation of governmental policies and the management of public programs and services. Literature in this field covers diverse topics such as organizational behavior, public policy analysis, bureaucratic structures, governance, and the delivery of public services. Key themes include understanding how public organizations function, including leadership dynamics, decision-making processes, organizational culture, and employee motivation.

Additionally, research examines the formulation, implementation, and evaluation of public policies, exploring the political, economic, and social factors that influence these

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Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

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processes and their impacts on society. Ethical considerations, accountability mechanisms, public sector reforms, and the role of technology in improving service delivery are also significant areas of exploration. Comparative and international perspectives provide insights into variations in administrative practices across different contexts, while studies on innovation, collaboration, sustainability, and crisis management reflect ongoing efforts to address contemporary challenges facing public administrations worldwide.

The mission of the Department of Education is generally to promote student achievement and preparation for global competitiveness by fostering educational excellence and ensuring equal access to high-quality education. Specific goals and focus areas of the Department may vary but its ultimate goal is to provide inclusive education to learners in all regions of the country. Every child should have access to school, learning and that no one will be left behind.

To wit in order to achieve the Department of Education mandate, teaching staff and including the non-teaching personnel work together, actively engaged and share their responsibility to provide services that will benefit not only the learners, other stakeholder but also the community.

The findings of this research show that most of the procedures and processes on records management of the division were followed but there are opportunities for improvement to be addressed to enhance the delivery of services to clients of the division.

In accordance with the result, division of DepEd Tarlac province may consider reviewing and revisiting some of the existing procedures and processes especially in disposition process to create action and preventive measures for better delivery of services and easy transactions in the division. They may also consider providing additional trainings and seminars to employees to ensure they are competent and efficient to their post.

Also, to solve issues of clients such as lack of assistance and personnel in-charge is not accommodating they may consider creating a page, website or social media platform intended for Records Unit only that customers may access anytime. This may include all the information needed regarding the records unit transactions and may also be used to make a request regarding processes that may be done online. Staff augmentation may also be considered to ensure all the records unit process are conducted without delay.

In addition, they may create a program and policy that impose reprimand to those who will not follow the processes outlined for records management system and this could resolve the issue of employees neglecting the importance of records unit procedures.

Lastly, the division may consider to conduct regular review of the retention period of documents in the division office including documents in districts and schools to identify records that are needed and shall be retained as "permanent" and records that may have reached the prescribed retention period to practice the disposition process. Creation of a research team that focuses on records management, especially on disposition may also be considered. Members will conduct records management internal audit, review records within the division office, visit to districts and schools to collect and analyze practices and synthesize the findings to develop recommendations for improvement of the current processes in records management.

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Chapter 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the findings from the data gathered and the conclusions drawn. In addition, the researcher formulated recommendations relative to the problems stated.

Summary of Findings

1. The evaluation of compliance on records management in terms of receiving obtained a grand mean of 4.51 or always complied.
2. The records unit action relative to encoding obtained a grand mean of 4.33 or often complied.
3. A grand mean of 4.55 or always complied was rated by the respondents along with filing on records management.
4. The evaluation of records unit action relative to retrieving obtained a grand mean of 4.48 or often complied.
5. A grand mean of 4.38 or often complied was rated by the respondents along with the records unit action on releasing.
6. The evaluation of the records unit action relative to disposition obtained a grand mean of 1.8 or rarely complied.
7. Overall evaluation of compliance on records management at DepEd Tarlac Province was 4.00 or often complied.
8. The correlation between the compliance on records management along with receiving, retrieving, releasing and satisfaction of the respondents obtained p -value of 0.499, 0.060, and 0.412 respectively.
9. The correlation between the compliance on records management along with encoding, filing and satisfaction of the respondents both obtained 0 p -value.
10. Based on the survey result the topmost problem encountered by the respondents was different records unit actions were not delivered on time with a frequency of 64 or 22.30% while the least problem encountered was clients were not allowed to provide insights, opinions, suggestions to further improved services with a frequency of 7 or 2.44%.
11. The division may consider to create policy that impose reprimand to those who will not follow the procedures outlined for records management in the division to resolve the issue of neglecting the importance of records unit processes which is one of the preventive measures and action plans proposed by the researcher.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study.

1. The majority of the respondents rated the compliance on records management along with receiving as always complied, however there was 1 statement rated as often complied since the personnel in-charge move hastily in order to finish transaction quickly and prevent long queue. Also, the slow and intermittent internet connectivity in the records unit contributes to the delayed processing of documents.
2. Overall compliance on records management relative to encoding was rated by the respondents as often complied wherein 1 statement was rated as always complied but the other 3 statements were rated by the respondents as often complied.

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3. The records unit action relative to filing was rated by the respondents as always complied, however the process on division memoranda copies are properly filed and safekept was rated by the respondents as often complied since it depends on the process of other unit in the division.
4. The compliance on records management relative to retrieving was rated by the respondents as always complied, however there was statement stipulated which perceived to be often complied such as: if the document requested cannot be located the personnel in charge informs the requisitioner and provides alternative action.
5. The overall compliance on records management relative to releasing was rated by the respondents as often complied since there is a lack of employee that will handle the records unit action in terms of releasing.
6. The records unit action relative to disposition was rated by the respondent as rarely complied. This is because no unit in the division declared records for disposal, thus documents were considered as active files and has permanent retention period.
7. The overall evaluation of the compliance on records management at DepEd Tarlac Province was often complied.
8. The correlation between the compliance on records management along with receiving, retrieving, releasing and satisfaction of the respondents obtained p-value higher than the 0.05 alpha level. Then, the null hypothesis is accepted thus, there is no significant relationship between compliance on records management in terms of receiving, retrieving, releasing, and the level of satisfaction of the respondents.
9. The correlation between the compliance on records management along with encoding, filing, and satisfaction of the respondents obtained p-value lower than the 0.05 alpha level. Then, the null hypothesis is rejected thus, there is a significant relationship between compliance on records management in terms of encoding, filing and the level of satisfaction of the respondents
10. The topmost concern of the respondents was the records unit actions were not delivered on time which were prolonged because of lack of personnel to receive bulk number of documents from schools and districts. Also, slow internet connectivity is a contributing factor in delayed processing of documents.
11. The division may provide programs or activities for employees in order to more effective and efficient in their field of work and create policy that impose reprimand to those who will not follow the procedures outlined for records management in the division to resolve the issue of neglecting the importance of records unit processes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were derived based on the findings and conclusions of the study.

1. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may review and revisit the procedures and processes on records management to discover which process could be simplified and improved.
2. The division may consider to conduct regular review of the retention period of documents in the division office including documents in districts and schools to identify records that are needed and shall be retained as "permanent" and records that may have reached the prescribed retention period to practice the disposition process.
3. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may consider to add employee in the records unit to ensure on time delivery of services.

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

4. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may consider to upgrade existing internet connectivity or provide stable internet connection to records unit to prevent delay in the processing of documents.
5. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may provide trainings and seminars for employees to enhance their competencies.
6. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may create program and policy that impose reprimand to those who will not follow the processes outlined for records management system to ensure employees are guided and prevent confusion in the procedures.
7. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may benchmark practices of records management from other divisions and organizations to improve processes and migrate to full electronic transactions if possible.
8. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may consider practicing records digitization in the whole division of Tarlac Province including districts and schools such as digital preservation and disaster recovery planning to mitigate risks to records integrity and ensure continued access to valuable information over time.
9. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may consider to review research-driven approaches and encourage innovation among employees regarding records management. This may include studying emerging technologies, methodologies and case studies to advance the division's understanding and improve existing practices for efficiency, effectiveness and sustainability.
10. The division of DepEd Tarlac Province may consider to create research team that focuses on records management especially on disposition. It may involve records unit employees that gone through series of trainings on records management, auditing, law, and information technology disciplines. Members will conduct records management internal audit, review records within the division office, visit to districts and schools to collect and analyze practices and synthesize the findings to develop recommendations for improvement of the current processes in records management.

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Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

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Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.35-90, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Unegbu, Vincent E; Adenike, Oludipe Bolaji(2013) *Challenges of Records Management Practices in the Ministry Of Information and Strategy, Lagos State, Nigeria* at International Research: Journal of Library and Information Science; Aligarh Vol. 3, Iss. 2.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13309373

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